

STUDENT ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND MOTIVATION OF VIRTUAL
MATHEMATICS VIA ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING

EVAN PLORGO TAJA-ON

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Department of Science Education

APPROVAL SHEET

This master's thesis attached hereto entitle, "STUDENT ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND MOTIVATION OF VIRTUAL MATHEMATICS VIA ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING" (Research No. G-20543), prepared and submitted by EVAN P. TAJA-ON, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Science in Mathematics Education, is hereby accepted.

(Sgd.)
RAUL C. ORONGAN, Ph.D.
Chair, Thesis Advisory Committee
Date: January 7, 2022

(Sgd.)
DENIS A. TAN, Ph.D.
Examiner
Date: January 7, 2022

(Sgd.)
CHERLY C. CORDOVA, Ph.D.
Member, Thesis Advisory Committee
Date: January 12, 2022

(Sgd.)
ZITA I. DALES, Ph.D.
Examiner
Date: December 15, 2021

(Sgd.)
JOEMAR B. CAPUYAN, Ph.D.
Member, Thesis Advisory Committee
Date: January 12, 2022

Recommending Approval:

(Sgd.)
EHLRICH RAY J. MAGDAY
Chairperson, Science Education Department
Date: January 12, 2022

(Sgd.)
RAUL C. ORONGAN, Ph.D.
College Research Coordinator
Date: January 12, 2022

Accepted in partial fulfillment for the requirements for the degree of Master of Science in Mathematics Education.

Approved:

(Sgd.)
GLADYS S. ESCARLOS, Ph.D.
College Dean
Date: January 12, 2022

Noted:

(Sgd.)
JUPITER V. CASAS, Ph.D.
Director of Research
Date: January 12, 2022

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

The proponent of this study was born on the [REDACTED], in the City of Malaybalay, Bukidnon, to [REDACTED] and [REDACTED]. Being raised with so much love, affection, and guidance enabled him to grow and foster within the limit of simplicity.

He completed his primary education at [REDACTED]. He attended his secondary education at [REDACTED] under the [REDACTED]. He then enrolled at [REDACTED], graduated with a Bachelor of [REDACTED], and garnered the [REDACTED] in [REDACTED].

After his graduation, he took and passed the Career Service Professional Examination and Teachers Licensure Examination in [REDACTED]. He then enrolled at [REDACTED]. took a course in Bookkeeping. He was certified by the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority and earned his [REDACTED] in Bookkeeping. In January of 2019, he enrolled in the graduate program in the Masters of Science in Mathematics Education at Central Mindanao University. In [REDACTED], he got employed at [REDACTED] as a college instructor under the School of Education.

EVAN PLORGO TAJA-ON

DEDICATION

The researcher dedicates this study to his family for their undying support, prayers, understanding, comfort, and love for this work that reassured and motivated the researcher.

The researcher also dedicates this study to his friends and colleagues for their unwavering support, prayers, motivation, and for being there throughout the hustles and bustles of life.

Above all, the researcher dedicates this study to the Almighty Father, the great provider of wisdom and strength, and with whom this work is highly indebted and dedicated. To God be the glory forever and ever!

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ABSTRACT

TAJA-ON, EVAN PLORGO, Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, Region X, Philippines, December 2021, Student Academic Achievement and Motivation of Virtual Mathematics via Online Collaborative Learning

Adviser: RAUL C. ORONGAN, Ph.D.

The adaptation of virtual learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has seriously affected the students, teachers, and different learning institutions. The abrupt change has affected the students' academic achievement and motivation in learning, especially in Mathematics. Online Collaborative Learning (OCL) is a learning approach that engages students to cooperate in learning and accomplish a learning task. The study aims to assess OCL in teaching, engaging, and developing mathematical concepts among students and measure the effectiveness of OCL in virtual instruction. The study implemented a quasi-experimental design with the college students taking Mathematics as participants. The study utilized a content-validated achievement test to measure performance. For non-academic assessment, the study adopted the Team Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ) developed by the London Leadership Academy and the Motivation to Learn Online Questionnaire (MLOQ) formulated by S. Fowler.

The post-test result showed very satisfactory performance for OCL and fair performance for the non-OCL. The performance in Mathematics of the students exposed to OCL is significantly higher than students who were not exposed to OCL, as revealed by the post-test scores. Students' motivation in both groups considering the seven factors are significantly different except for social engagement. Overall, the students' motivation for those exposed to OCL is significantly higher than those students not exposed to OCL based on MLOQ

results. The effectiveness of the student in both groups considering the eight dimensions of effectiveness is significantly different. Overall, students' effectiveness among those exposed to OCL is significantly higher than students not exposed to OCL based on the TEQ result.

Keywords: Academic Achievement; Motivation; Virtual Mathematics; Online Collaboration.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Online teaching and learning are a challenge for many students and teachers alike. The teaching and learning of Mathematics are no exception to this challenge. Conventional teaching is now difficult, if not impossible, to conduct in this pandemic (Dizon, 2020). The challenge of every educational sector is how to deliver quality education to learners even without their physical presence. More so, the shift has also affected students' motivation to learn and engage (Baticulon et al., 2021). The researcher wants to use online collaborative learning to help alleviate the burden of teaching and learning Mathematics through virtual means. The COVID-19 pandemic hindered the learning of many students and burdened many institutions. Virtual Mathematics offers a setting for learning and developing mathematics concepts amongst the students. With the advent of technology and many social messaging applications, collaboration and communication among the students are easy and accessible (Al-Nofaie, 2020).

The researcher observed a significant decline in the learners' performance in Mathematics in the Modern World compared to the two previous academic years. During the academic year 2019-2020, the students' (n=278) overall grades averaged 1.90 ± 0.47 . While during the academic year 2020-2021, the students' (n=233) overall grades averaged 2.47 ± 1.02 . Mahyoob (2020) also supplements this claim as many learners have difficulty learning their subject in the virtual or online classroom. According to Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela (2020), every school around the country struggles to provide quality instruction to students enrolled in their programs. The problem is the students' academic performance and their motivation to continue learning.

Harasim (2012) suggested that an online collaborative approach can create an avenue for learners to cooperate and help foster learning and motivation through peer mentoring and feedbacking with the teachers' assistance. The online classroom is a new trend in education, offering a new approach to distance learning, especially in this time of pandemics (Oraif and Elyas, 2021). The shift of many institutions from face-to-face instruction to online learning instruction is challenging for the students and teachers. Distance online education provides access to flexible and accessible learning and has accommodated many learners since its establishment and usage in the educational setting (Andrade, Miller, Kunz, and Ratliff, 2020). According to Nguyen (2015), online learning is, at least, as effective as traditional or face-to-face classes.

Online Collaborative Learning (OCL), as an approach presented by Magen-Nagar and Shonfeld (2018), suggests the use of collaboration in teaching and learning. Lai, Wen, Gao, and Lin (2020) described that an individual spends plenty of time on the internet, browsing social media, and running search engine platforms. Chua (2021) emphasized that the Philippines ranked number one among the social media users for six years running, with an average of four hours and fifteen minutes each day. Hence, the research utilized Facebook messenger and Facebook as a way for students to communicate with one another.

Google Classroom's user-friendly system and varied features help students and teachers establish a classroom setting at home. Google Classroom is also accessible for learners and easy to manage for teachers. Hence, the research utilized the Google platform for delivery and assessment. Virtual education shows potential in teaching the contents of courses. The learning process offered by virtual education demonstrates a positive effect, such as the increase in interactivity between the student and teacher, an easier way to absorb the content of the subject, an increase in student motivation, and the interest of the students to learn (Fernando, Thiry, Queiroz, and Fernandes, 2020). Furthermore, the study of Barbour (2015) found out that students

experience similar learning in an online classroom and a traditional classroom. Studies suggested that using the online platform encouraged the students to learn and significantly increased the learners' academic performance and motivation to learn (Shang and Chen, 2018).

This study focused on the online collaboration of the student to teach and help one another in learning their lessons for Mathematics. The study examined whether using online collaboration significantly affected the students' performance and motivation in learning Mathematics in a virtual classroom.

Statement of the Problem

The main purpose of this study is to assess the use of a virtual collaborative approach to teach, engage, and develop the concepts of Mathematics among the students.

The study investigated the effectiveness of online collaborative learning in virtual instruction in teaching Mathematics.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the level of student academic achievement when exposed to online collaborative learning and exposed to online non-collaborative learning in the following:
 - a) pretest; and
 - b) posttest?
2. What is the degree of motivation of students in online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning in the following;
 - a) intrinsic goal orientation;
 - b) extrinsic goal orientation;
 - c) control of learning beliefs;
 - d) self-efficacy;
 - e) test anxiety;

- f) class context; and
- g) social engagement?

3. What is the extent on the effectiveness dimension of students in online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning in the following;

- a) purpose and goals;
- b) roles;
- c) process;
- d) relationships;
- e) intergroup relations;
- f) problem solving;
- g) passion and commitment; and
- h) skills and learning?

4. Is there a significant difference in the academic achievement of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning?

5. Is there a significant difference in the motivation of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning in the following;

- a) intrinsic goal orientation;
- b) extrinsic goal orientation;
- c) control of learning beliefs;
- d) self-efficacy;
- e) test anxiety;
- f) class context; and
- g) social engagement?

6. Is there a significant difference in the effectiveness dimension of students to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning in the following;

- a) purpose and goals;
- b) roles;
- c) process;
- d) relationships;
- e) intergroup relations;

- f) problem solving;
- g) passion and commitment; and
- h) skills and learning?

Objective of the Study

The study investigated the effectiveness of online collaborative learning in virtual instruction in teaching Mathematics on students' achievement and motivation.

Specifically, the study has the following objectives:

1. to compare the level of student academic achievement among those exposed to online collaborative learning and exposed to online non-collaborative learning in the following:
 - a) pretest; and
 - b) posttest.
2. to ascertain the degree of motivation of students in online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning in the following;
 - a) intrinsic goal orientation;
 - b) extrinsic goal orientation;
 - c) control of learning beliefs;
 - d) self-efficacy;
 - e) test anxiety;
 - f) class context; and
 - g) social engagement.
3. to assess the dimension level of students in online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning in the following;
 - a) purpose and goals;
 - b) roles;
 - c) process;
 - d) relationships;

- e) intergroup relations;
- f) problem solving;
- g) passion and commitment; and
- h) skills and learning.

4. to determine whether a significant difference exist in the academic achievement of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning.

5. to find out whether there is a significant difference in the motivation of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning in the following:

- a) purpose and goals;
- b) roles;
- c) process;
- d) relationships;
- e) intergroup relations;
- f) problem solving;
- g) passion and commitment; and
- h) skills and learning.

6. to differentiate the effectiveness dimension among the students who were exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning in the following;

- a) purpose and goals;
- b) roles;
- c) process;
- d) relationships;
- e) intergroup relations;
- f) problem solving;
- g) passion and commitment; and
- h) skills and learning.

Significance of the Study

The study is beneficial in identifying the effectiveness of using virtual collaboration among students and developing Mathematical learning through a virtual medium. The study is constructive in developing students' engagement through virtual interaction and collaboration through social media platforms with the teacher's guidance. The study offered the student a medium of communication and cooperation for learning their lessons. This study guided the learners in learning mathematical concepts with the teacher's guidance. It also provided an outlet for many students to interact and communicate with others. Some learners are confined in their homes and are often left to themselves while their parents work. Furthermore, learners benefited from its user-friendly settings to communicate with the teacher and their groupmates with social media.

This study is beneficial for the teachers (not only in the field of Mathematics) as it could provide an avenue for educators to develop a strategy for teaching in a virtual platform while also incorporating some traditional and innovative methods. The finding would help the teachers lessen the burden of online teaching and create an experiential learning model where students learn through collaborative and digital/virtual methods.

Moreover, the institution benefited from the study as it became the basis for other online learning and virtual mathematics researchers. This study provided relevant data on the effectiveness of virtual collaboration in this time of the pandemic. Furthermore, the study also evaluated the students' satisfaction in an online learning system.

Scope and Delimitation

This study is delimited only to one teaching strategy, the use of Online Collaborative Learning (OCL) in conjunction with virtual teaching and learning of Mathematics. The conduct of the study was among the college students at San Isidro College (SIC). The platforms utilized for the implementation of this study were Google Classroom, Google Meet, Google Forms, and Facebook Messenger. The delimitation of the study is the lessons on the measures of central tendency, measures of variability, sampling techniques, and hypothesis testing.

The students enrolled in the Statistics course at San Isidro College experienced the instruction. There were two sections with forty-seven (47) students that experienced online collaborative learning and two other sections with fifty-one (51) students that experienced non-collaborative learning. Both groups were subject to virtual Mathematics with a learner-centered approach to learning.

Definition of Terms

The following terms used in the study are defined operationally and conceptually:

Academic Achievement refers to the educational goals attained by the students after a course.

Class Content, as used in the study, refers to the lessons taken in class.

Control of Learning Beliefs, as used in the study, refers to students' perception of their learning behavior and performance.

Effectiveness refers to the student's productiveness in learning.

Intergroup Relations refer to the interaction between the students.

Intrinsic Goal Orientation, as used in the study, refers to the internal motivation of the student to learn.

Extrinsic Goal Orientation, as used in the study, refers to the external motivation of the students to learn.

Motivation refers to the students' desire to act or learn.

Online Collaborative Learning refers to a breakout session with teacher support from one group to another (Harasim, 2012). Students work collectively in an online modality to solve a problem or finish a task.

Online Learning refers to the process of learning through the use of technology.

Online Motivation refers to the students' drive to finish a task or complete an activity in the virtual setting.

Online Non-Collaborative Learning, as used in this study, the term refers to a learning approach where students are facilitated in their learning using the online platform (Gutierrez, 2013). Schools implemented the learning approach during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Passion and Commitment refer to the students' drive to learn and accomplish the learning task.

Peer-Review refers to the assistance offered by each member of the team to check and feedback another member's work.

Problem Solving, as used in the study, refers to the analysis of the student on the problem to achieve an effective solution.

Process refers to the direction of work taken by the learners to attain the learning goals.

Purpose and Goals, as used in the study, refer to the outcome of the learning task.

Relationships refer to the connection or interdependence of the students in the learning process.

Roles refer to the position assigned by the group to an individual during a specific task.

Team refers to the group of students working collaboratively to attain and accomplish a goal or task and where leadership is rotational.

Test-Anxiety refers to factors affecting the students' ability to perform on a test.

Self-Efficacy refers to the ability of the student to manage and organize a situation.

Skills and Learning, as used in the study, refer to the development of the student.

Social Engagement refers to the student's participation in the class or the group.

Virtual Mathematics refers to mathematics teaching and learning in an online setting and is implemented through Online Learning Platforms.

Virtual Teaching refers to the medium of teaching that delivers instruction and information to students/learners using technology. Virtual Teaching is usually done with the aid of technology and applications.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter contains the review and related literature and related studies, the conceptual framework, the theoretical framework, the research paradigm, and the study's hypothesis. It further elaborates the relationship among academic achievement in online learning, online motivation, virtual Mathematics, and online collaboration.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Virtual Mathematics and Academic Achievement in Online Learning

Following the spread of the COVID-19 virus, the trends in teaching and learning have shifted in the online setting and follow a synchronous and asynchronous model of lesson delivery (Al-Nofaie, 2020). The learning process has become technocentric in nature, and the development of the technological didactics trend to connect students and teachers has surfaced (Pando, 2018). The pedagogical practices have drastically evolved with adherence to the internet, the ever-growing source of information, and the imperative role of educational agents within virtual learning (Hernandez et al., 2019).

Teaching mathematics online is not a new trend, but due to COVID-19, educators re-envisioned the teaching of Mathematics online and presented a virtual delivery method for their learners (Figg, Khirwadkar, and Welbourn, 2020). A study by Reiten (2020) encourages educators to use virtual Mathematics as a reteaching tool to support students learning, develop understanding, and provide in-the-moment feedback. Kim and Park (2018) suggested using applications and technology to help visualize and understand the teaching of Mathematics.

Virtual learning utilizes technology and varied software with a connection to the internet. Educational institutions use virtual learning to enhance the learning of students. Teaching and learning in a virtual setting are through the different learning platforms where learners and teachers are not physically present (Racheva, 2017). Bates (2014) stated that in the digital age, the experience given to the learners would support the development of knowledge and skill needed not only in Mathematics but also in online learning.

Teaching Mathematics on an online platform adapts the current paradigm of teaching in the digital era of the twenty-first century that enhances connectivity and interactivity among teachers and learners alike (Ahn and Edwin, 2018). According to Eric (2015), a strong foundation and experience are required to learn and understand mathematical concepts. Through gaining experience, learners can develop the necessary skills to identify a problem, use reasoning to create a valid argument, and apply abstract Mathematical concepts in real-life scenarios.

Since technology has also changed the way people communicate and interact with one another, the intricacies of learning Mathematics can be guided and assisted with mobile and online communication (Huang, Kellert, Manouchehri, 2015). A virtual setting for teaching Mathematics is a challenging undertaking for any teacher or institution as it does not simulate the hands-on nature of Mathematics. However, the study of Figg, Khirwadkar, and Welbourn (2020) compensates for the difficulty of virtually teaching mathematics, promotes computational thinking among learners, and helps understand the concepts of Mathematics.

The observation on using mobile devices and software applications to have supported the mathematical analysis of children and the visualization techniques was also developed (Tucker et al., 2017). The usage of mobile devices for learning may affect the learners in different ways. The observation on the learners in the study conducted by Moyer-Packenham et al. (2015) displayed an increase in performance and efficiency in mathematics while other learners displayed no rise or a similar result before using virtual learning.

A study conducted by Deniz and Simsek (2015) showed that using virtual tools and communication in teaching mathematics results in a positive effect on students' learning and improves student success in mathematics classes and courses. A study conducted by Kim and Park (2018) shows that teachers using virtual Mathematics to deliver lessons had an increased ineffectiveness. The activities that teachers gave to their learners enhanced students learning.

Demitriadou, Stavroulia, and Lanitis (2020) contradicted the positive effect of the virtual teaching of Mathematics, stating that there was no improvement in the students' performance or there was no impact on the students' academic performance or efficiency in Mathematics. However, the suggestion of Matranga and Koku (2015) states that to improve virtual Mathematics teaching, the interaction between learners and teacher must establish the support mechanism provided by a collaboration that cultivates a healthy community of learning and development for the learners.

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced schools to shift from face-to-face learning to an online form of education (Al-Nofaie, 2020). Many universities worldwide have encouraged online learning to promote students' positive attitudes towards learning (Abudmaid, 2020). Learning with the use of technology is not new in the Philippine setting. Online learning has been used even before the pandemic. Technology has played a vital role in teaching and learning as it supplements the educational system and gives students and learners easy access to information (Kondakciu, 2020).

Studies suggested that using the online platform encouraged the students to learn and significantly increased the learners' academic performance and motivation to learn (Shang and Chen, 2018). With access to the internet, students can facilitate their learning, learn at their own pace and perform and submit their tasks according to their own time (Maxwell, Smoker, and Stites-Doe, 2018). According to Sze (2020), Google Classroom is one of the most accessible and easy-to-use learning platforms so far.

Effectiveness in Online Learning

Online learning has several dimensions to consider to measure its effectiveness in student learning (London Leadership Academy, n.d.). One dimension is the purpose and goals of learning; student must set their goals in learning in order for them to have the drive to learn and attain that goal at the end of the class or even towards the end of the semester (Moyer-Packenham et al., 2015). Students must also identify or realize the purpose of learning to associate meaning for their efforts in learning the subject matter (Reyes-Chau, 2020).

Another dimension is the roles that the students must play in learning. Students must know their roles in order for them to have an established identity and can be a basis of effective learning (Serin, 2017). The student's relationship and interrelations with one another also factor in as students are naturally interactive and desire to interact with one another; these interactions will help the students learn with the exchange of information (Oraif and Elyas, 2021).

The dimension of problem-solving is another to consider on effectiveness as the ability of the students to analyze and solve a problem is a crucial aspect of the learning (Raymundo, 2021). When done in a collaborative method, problem-solving can help students easily understand the problem because of peer feedback and the comprehensive discussion that will help them recognize the problem. Additionally, it would be easier to solve and arrive at a quick answer (Balairos, 2020).

The dimension of passion and commitment plays a role in the students' ability to continue learning with desire and obligation to attain the intended learning outcome at the end of the learning session. The commitment to learning extends beyond the classroom and manifests as a desire to improve themselves (Magsabol, 2021). Moreover, the last dimension is the student's development of skills and learning. The students' skills are not necessarily physical but also mental and emotional. These skills and learning manifest through (Abudmaid, 2020)

An observation on the use of technology in the classroom by Purcell, Buchanan, and Friedrich (2013) has significantly improved the learning performance. Technology has helped educators teach students from the middle and high school levels. With easy access to the internet nowadays, information is readily and easily available for students. With the varied search engines and information platforms, the enthrallment of students is unavoidable with the overwhelming amount of data and the palm of their hands (Condict, 2016). The immediate response of the educational sectors of the Philippines by introducing e-learning and online classrooms has enhanced the countries situation during the quarantine period (Reyes-Chua, E. et al. 2020).

According to the study of Shang and Chen (2018), there is a significant improvement in the learners' reading skills, and the learners' test scores have significantly improved in an online learning mode of lesson delivery and assessment. Online learning has marginally improved students' learning process (Andrade, Miller, Kunz, and Ratliff, 2020). The online learning experience by the students, according to the study of Paulsen and McCormick (2020), suggested the learning environment and learning strategies have nothing to do with the implementation but rather the characteristics of the learners that play a significant role in learning.

However, there are also downsides to the shift in instruction. Bird, Castleman, and Lohner (2020) found decreased course completers with increased withdrawal and failures due to the change to online instruction. The Philippines is no exception to these problems. Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela (2020) claimed that the higher education institutions (HEIs) mean alternative learning, and technologies used for delivering instruction to students still have gaps and challenges. A recommendation from their study was that innovation for education should be grounded on a more profound realization of distance learning. Although the e-learning platforms used by the schools in the Philippines are free, teachers still encounter problems with the lack of resources, connectivity, and training for both learners and teachers (Kelly, 2019; Reyes-Chua et al., 2020).

A frequent encounter with the difficulties learners face in an online learning system is their difficulty adjusting their learning styles, the performance of their responsibilities between school and at home, and the poor communication and connection between students and teachers (Baticulon et al. 2021). Lee and Haggerty (2020) state that less fortunate students and families living in slums and isolated areas would have difficulty accessing online learning for reasons like money, location, internet access, and devices, unlike students and families who can afford and possess better quality devices.

The amount of time spent by the learners on the internet and social media platforms has significantly exposed them to much information. This information may help them in their studies or distract them (Chua, 2021). To maximize the result of online learning, the institution with their teachers must plan the activities and assessment ahead of time to save time and resources and to provide a conducive learning environment for its learners (Shan and Chen 2018; Akhter and Mahmood, 2018; Andrade, Miller, Kunz, and Ratliff, 2020).

Online collaborative learning offers and applies the concept of online classrooms as a mode of delivery for education. The learner can learn in the comforts of their homes or at the mere swipe of their fingers. Many educators use the online delivery mode to teach their students and promote a paperless output (Abuhmaid, 2020). With access to the internet, the learners can search for information within seconds and deliver it within minutes (Condict, 2016). Since the advancement of technology, it is seldom that an individual encounters a student without a cellular phone or access to the internet (Purcell, Buchanan, and Friedrich, 2013). Chua (2021) specified that the Philippines ranked the highest on internet usage worldwide, clocking with an average of ten hours and fifty-six minutes spent on the internet.

Online submissions of outputs and tasks have a positive impact on students learning. Maxwell, Smoker, and Stites-Doe (2018) wrote that students preferred online methods of turning in and have significantly increased their engagement in their classes. The implementation of social media as a tool for

learning and the many kinds of research promoting the potential of social media for learning. According to Lai, Wen, Gao, and Lin (2020), social media platforms have significantly improved and influenced students' learning and perception of school works.

Online learning provides learners the control of their time and their education. Teachers need to guide the learners to maximize the learning input and provide quality output while managing their time on the different subjects they enrolled in (Gutierrez, 2013). Online learning places a heavy emphasis that students taking full responsibility for their learning and inquiry. Educators provide problems for students to work on and guide the teachers to arrive at a viable solution (Stephan, 2014).

Motivation in Online Learning

Distance learning is not new to education but positively impacts learners' motivation and lessens their anxiety towards taking tests (Bonito, 2013). The educational sector is moderately successful in implementing online learning and shows that students are motivated to use educational devices and applications (Avila et al., 2020).

Student motivation in online learning has several factors to consider, and these factors may affect students' performance in learning (Fowler, 2017). Student motivation plays an integral role in the learning process and their drive to continue learning online (Bonito, 2013). One factor is the intrinsic goal orientation to learn, which is the internal factor of motivation or the self-motivation that affects the student's motivation, like their goals and beliefs (Chua, 2021). While the extrinsic goal orientation, which is the external factor of motivation to learn, affects the students' motivation like grades and rewards (Estira, 2020). The study of Abun, Magallanez, Agoot, and Barroga (2019) discovered that the action between the academic student's academic performance to their intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Additionally, students' attitudes may play in their motivation to learn. Their attitude towards learning a particular topic will also influence their motivation to learn (Castro, 2018).

Another factor is the control of learning beliefs. Students regulate their own beliefs of the purpose of learning and establish a reason for learning because of this belief. The students learning beliefs can be influenced by their peers or classmates and can help them establish their purpose for learning (Avila et al., 2020). A person's belief will significantly impact their perspective of specific lessons and activities. If the lesson that is being taught is in line with a student's belief, this will improve their motivation to learn the lesson; the opposite is also true (Napil and San Jose, 2020). Students can be motivated to learn online with proper assistance and reassurance. The guidance will impact students' beliefs and encourage them to learn the materials and lessons (Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020).

The student's self-efficacy is also one factor because they are determined to perform a task or activity confidently. Their self-efficacy is also a driving force needed in an online class due to the independence in learning and independent work (Chyung, Moll, and Berg, 2010). The study of Fulgencio et al. (2021) stated that students' self-efficacy could significantly affect their academic motivation amidst the COVID-19 pandemic and the online learning modality.

The factor of text anxiety plays heavily on the ability of the students to take quizzes and exams. Text anxiety will affect the students' ability to perform, and the higher their anxiety, the more likely they will have low scores on tests given in class (Subin, 2021). Text anxiety is a personal factor that affects students. It may be affected by varying factors like knowledge-possessed rewards at the end of the test or overall confidence to take the test. Students who are more equipped with the knowledge have lesser anxiety than students who have not prepared themselves or have not studied that well for the test (Reyes and Castillo, 2015).

The class content is also a factor to consider, as when materials are too complicated for students or are not explained well, it will diminish their motivation to learn (Gocotano et al., 2021). Moreover, the last factor is social engagement; students and people, in general, are naturally interactive. When

students interact with their peers or classmates, they may play a role in improving or contributing to their motivation (Oraif and Elyas, 2021).

With the abrupt shift in instruction, learning online has become a challenge to both learner and teacher. Without face-to-face interaction, teachers have now lost the ability to perceive the students' non-verbal cues, which helped indicate the learners' emotions and reactions to the lessons. The anonymous ambiance of online classrooms can stimulate learners to withdraw, lessen participation, or completely disappear from the enrolled course. This lack of motivation may be associated with the learners' belief that online courses are easier to take and do not require plenty of time, making them prone to disengagement before the class begins (Cull, 2010).

A study conducted by Mese and Sevilen (2021) claimed that online education negatively affects students' motivation to learn. This loss of enthusiasm instigates the lack of social interaction between learners and teachers, the mismatch between personal expectations and actual content, organizational problems, and the coordination of the learning environments. Tamma (2020) further explains the negative impact on the motivation of online learning. Primarily, online learning causes learners to be socially isolated and thus makes the learners disengaged in discussions and activities. Secondly, online learning lacks face-to-face communication increasing the students' anxiety to participate due to the lack of non-verbal cues and slow feedback mechanism. Moreover, online learning lacks the necessary precautions to cheat and thus encourages students to cheat during assessments or quizzes, which lessens their motivation to learn.

The study of Chyung, Moll, and Berg (2010) contradicts the negative impact of online learning on students' motivation. Their research discovered that online learning has significantly improved the students' motivation and has made a significant contribution to education. Tammb (2020) expounded on the positive impact of online learning and motivation. Primarily, online learning is self-paced, allowing learners to work on their requirements in their own time. Learners who want to work on it early in the morning or late at night may do it

in their leisure. Secondly, online learning is student-centered, creating a student-friendly academic endeavor and captivating learners because of its self-paced nature. Furthermore, online learning adjusts to the learners' learning styles due to the flexible nature of online learning that fits all types of students at once.

Harandi (2015) suggested a strong relationship between online learning and students' motivation, and students are more likely to be motivated when conducting classes in the digital setting. The study of Lee and Martin (2017) revealed that extrinsically driven students are more likely to participate in online discussions and obtain a higher grade than those who are more intrinsically motivated. On the other hand, Malinauska and Pozeriene (2020) claimed that students have a higher intrinsic motivation in an online class and are more active in class discussions and activities.

According to Kim and Frick (2011), motivation can change depending on the learners' perception of online learning, like perceived relevance to course, quality of instruction, familiarity with technology or platform, and personal motives to finish the course. Ucar and Goksel (2020) establish that social media platforms, specifically Facebook™, have significantly increased the students' motivation to engage in online learning since Facebook is a supplementary tool for student learning.

The word 'cheating' has changed in the digital classroom. Many textbooks have been digitalized and uploaded to the world wide web. The activities can easily be browsed, and many have attached answers. Resourceful students take advantage of this and do not answer their activities independently (Rowan and Murray, 2021). Many textbook activities and shared study materials are now available on online websites and easily accessible by students. Many experts and educators believe that the shift to online education has drastically affected learners' ability to learn and retain information. Students only intend to cheat in their activities (Subin, 2021).

Many instructors are wary of students' possibilities in their online activities and quizzes. According to Schaffhauser (2020), around 93% of educators believe online instructors are more favorable to academic dishonesty. According to Magsabol (2021), many students would pay others to accomplish their work rather than do it independently. The finding was linked to the overwhelming academic workload that the student has and would resort to paying others to lessen the burden.

Aduayi-Akue et al. (2017) discussed various factors that affect motivation to learn online. One related feature is the learner's internal factor in taking the course. Anxiety may build up within the student caused by the perceived difficulty, which would lead to cognitive overload and a decrease in motivation. However, well-structured lesson delivery and feedback mechanism may promote a learning flow, leading to sustained learner motivation in the virtual environment. Another factor is the external factor; these are the aspects of the students' learning environment. Learner support, in particular, affects the students' motivation to learn, and they need to interact with one another to overcome challenges in learning. The last factor is the personal factor; these are the motivational influences perceived and caused by the learner, e.g., their learning style and personal media preferences.

Students face many challenges in online learning, like connection, difficulty in understanding, and money-related factors, which can affect the learners' motivation to engage in online classes and activities (Gocotano et al., 2021). An important factor that affects students' online learning is socioeconomic status, but students are still highly motivated to learn online (Estira, 2020). On the contrary, students' motivation in online learning is not affected by other factors and displays no relationship between the learning strategies employed (Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020).

Collaboration in Online Learning

COVID-19 forced schools to shift to an online form of learning. Online learning follows a student-centered intervention for learning virtually to address

the different challenges during COVID-19 and beyond (Baticulon et al., 2021). Online collaborative learning (OCL) is encouraged because of its student-centered approach to learning. The online collaborative learning implemented in the study of Magen-Nagar and Shonfeld (2018) found an inversed trust among the learners with the use of technology. The result of the study indicated that online collaborative learning promotes a positive attitude towards online learning and develops students' self-confidence.

According to an article by Harasim (2012), The approach of OCL operates in an asynchronous and place-independent environment. OCL differs from other teaching and learning strategies. OCL defies traditional online learning, where reading is the primary source of information, and instruction and discussion are only complementary to education. OCL sees dialog as central to knowledge, and modules, hand-outs, and others function as supplementary mechanisms. The strategy of OCL enables students to engage in-class discussion freely and can log on anywhere that has access to the internet. Furthermore, in the OCL classroom, the role of the educator has shifted from being that of a provider to being more of a facilitator as learners are given more responsibility to their learning process and building discourse.

For collaboration to be successful, establishing healthy communication between participants is imperative to ensure student learning (Balsler, Grabau, Knieess, and Page, 2018). Virtual collaboration has generated conditions that displayed better learning gains due to the access of the internet for information and the easy division of tasks and communication between members (Lam and Kapur, 2018). Collaboration helps learners overcome challenges presented in the online learning modality by supporting each other and offering peer tutoring for topics least understood by the learner (Makel et al., 2020).

A structured approach to collaboration can help the overall success of the students in their activities. It is essential to provide feedback and monitor the learners' progress (Tan and Vicente, 2019). Additionally, the collaboration between students in a digital classroom can help them understand their lessons and improve their performance (Dizon, 2020). The study of Raymundo (2020)

states a positive correlation between students' creativity when working collaboratively. A collaborative approach can also improve a student's proficiency through group feedback and tutoring, improving the student's overall performance (Aguilar, 2019).

Weaknesses in OCL exist like the difficulty to scale learning and its complication to hand-on and experiment heavy disciplines and fields (Harasim, 2012). Barriers also exist with online collaboration, as presented in the study of Dreamson (2017), these barriers are: 1) real-time manipulation of tools and objects may increase the complexity of communication and interaction; 2) pre-recorded messages or videos and the invisibility of the group members may attenuate the overall quality and regularity of feedback from the teacher and or each other; and 3) the attitudes towards each member, individual learning goals, and the need to accomplish tasks and activities promptly may reduce the engagement of the learners and possibly increase the groups' reliance on the teacher to intervene.

An advantage of OCL is the high-level skill development like critical thinking and analytical thinking. OCL is at par with college classrooms which promotes deep learning and encourages discussion equal to or greater than face-to-face classrooms, which make up for its downsides (Harasim, 2012). Hammond (2017) suggested the following for a successful implementation of online collaboration; 1) the implementation of the different cooperative approaches is a must to foster the dynamic nature of each member of the group; 2) cooperation is constrained in nature and cooperation among group members must be structured and facilitated to bring out its motivational and cognitive advantages; 3) using media platforms can help create the necessary environment for learners to work together and achieve proper interaction; 4) technological advancement has brought about a change in the traditional teaching and learning, this has also impacted group collaboration and interaction.

Software such as Google Forms™, Google Docs™, and other platforms have an increased usage for online collaboration and activities. According to

Elizabeth and John (2012), using technology for learning has improved the sociability of the learners, learning fulfillment and created a positive online social environment. Furthermore, the usage of digital technology in education has a visible enhancement in the students' academic performance and the solution satisfaction of the learners. Using social media to make online collaboration more practical, like Facebook™, helps learners communicate, discuss topics and concepts, and plan with their members (Tarum, 2019; Ucar and Goksel, 2020).

With access to the internet, students can facilitate their learning, learn at their own pace and perform and submit their tasks according to their own time (Maxwell, Smoker, and Stites-Doe, 2018). According to Sze (2020), Google Classroom is one of the most accessible and easy-to-use learning platforms so far. Google Classroom's user-friendly system and varied features help students and teachers establish a classroom setting at home. Google Classroom is also accessible for learners and easy to manage for teachers. Hence, the research utilized the Google platform for delivery and assessment.

Technology integration is beneficial for the teacher as it engages students in active and discovery learning. Furthermore, a collaborative approach in the virtual teaching of mathematics (Figg, Khirwadkar, and Welbourn, 2020) promotes computational thinking among learners and pedagogical understanding of mathematics teaching. Collaboration is the backbone of learning. Educators collaborate to share their knowledge and help one another to grow. It is also true for students; collaboration is a teaching technique used in many classroom activities (Lam and Kapur, 2018). From simple paired activities to group performances. Social media facilitates online collaboration through many modes of the delivery system (Elizabeth and John, 2012).

According to Zhang (n.d.), OCL follows a structured approach to its implementation. First, general concepts are presented to the learners and are developed through divergent thinking and communication to generate ideas. Second, with the guidance and feedback of the instructor or teacher, students

compare, analyze, categorize, discuss, and argue about the ideas that each of them has. Finally, students synthesize their ideas and agree to develop the concepts further or generate new knowledge.

A small group with three to five members is better than a group with a larger population. Small groups foster a better rapport system and thus encourage learners to work amongst themselves, discuss the lesson, and help one another understand their lessons and or activities (Lee and Martin, 2017). The online interaction between each member of the group fosters peer-review culture. This culture provides students to check each other's work and give feedback to improve the effort of each individual in the group (Gautam, 2016; Stockleben et al., 2017). The interaction between the learners needs to foster trust. Trust among the members has been observed to influence online collaboration positively. The established trust can mediate by communication and interactivity among the members to cultivate a positive work environment and improve the quality of learning (Du et al., 2018).

Conceptual Framework

This study adheres to four learning theories: learner-centered learning theory, experiential learning theory, virtual learning theory, and collaborative learning theory. The study anchors on the notion that "students learn when they help each other and cooperate," and using an online collaborative approach in the current teaching and learning paradigm may address the learning concern in the pandemic (Hammond, 2017). The use of collaboration has also helped learners overcome challenges presented in the online learning modality by supporting each other and offering peer tutoring for topics least understood by the learner (Makel et al., 2020).

Learner-centered learning theory is an approach that focuses that learners have unique attributes and unbounded potential that call for a unique response in their learning. Additionally, the learner-centered approach sees learners desire to develop themselves and improve their learning (Williams, 2017). The student's academic achievement and motivation anchors on a learner-centered approach to teaching, which is the most viable for this study. In the student-centered approach for Mathematics, educators emphasize that students take full responsibility for problem-solving and inquiry for learning. Educators pose problems and guide the learners toward establishing a solution (Stephan, 2014). In an online setting, learners control their time and their learning. Teachers must guide the students in an online mode of lesson delivery to maximize their time and intake of information provided (Gutierrez, 2013).

Experiential learning theory follows the notion that learning is best if students experience the lessons and will help them retain information and facts better (McLeod, 2017). Academic achievement and motivation also anchor on experiential learning theory, one of the theories supporting this study. Mathematics requires experience to strengthen the learning and understanding of mathematical concepts. Through gaining experience by practicing and collaborating, learners can develop skills to identify problems, use reasoning to make a valid argument, and apply abstract mathematical concepts in a real-life situation (Eric, 2015). Secure experience in the digital age establishes a ground for developing knowledge and skills to support learning in the online setting (Bates, 2014).

Virtual learning or e-learning theory manages through activities that utilize and take advantage of multimedia platforms. Multimedia provides students with an alternative means of acquiring knowledge designed to enhance teaching and learning (Siemens, 2005). The virtual learning approach is a mode of teaching-learning adopted for this study due to COVID-19. Virtual learning utilizes computer and mobile devices to enhance the learning experience for learners in an educational organization. Conducting online teaching and learning activities means the teacher and learner are physically

separated (Racheva, 2017). Teaching Mathematics on an online platform adapts the current paradigm of teaching to the digital era of the twenty-first century that enhances connectivity and interactivity among teachers and learners alike (Ahn and Edwin, 2018).

Collaborative learning theory practices the idea that the best learning experience happens when students work together and actively participate in the learning process to accomplish the objective (Gillies, 2016). Interacting with other people helps foster experiences, and this, in turn, may be used to cultivate knowledge. The study applied online collaborative learning (OCL) coupled with virtual Mathematics to help strengthen the students learning in the instruction of mathematical concepts of the subject they enrolled in (Du et al. 2018). Since most learners possess gadgets and mobile devices, this can be utilized to communicate and learn mathematics with the instructor's guidance (Huang, Kellert, Manouchehri, 2015).

The intervention of this study is on collaborative learning. Online collaborative learning operates in an asynchronous environment. Online collaborative learning theory enables students to freely engage in in-class discussion and log on anywhere with access to the internet (Harasim, 2012). This study has two groups, the experimental and the controlled group. Both groups experienced virtual Mathematics with learner-centered instruction. Both groups were gauged on their experience OCL and evaluated using the researcher-made exam, considering the team effectiveness questionnaire (TEQ) and the motivation to learn online questionnaire (MLOQ). The data were treated statistically and interpreted based on the results.

Research Paradigm

Figure 1. Research paradigm of the study

Hypotheses of the Study

Given the complexity of virtual Mathematics coupled with the interactive and cooperative nature of online collaborative learning, the assumption is that online collaborative learning provided an avenue for developing mathematical thinking rather than the conventional learner-centered method of online instruction.

The following hypothesis was treated at a 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁ The academic achievement of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning is the same.
- H₀₂ The motivation of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning is the same.
- H₀₃ The team effectiveness of the students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning considering the dimensions is the same.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter deals with the methods and procedures used in the study. It includes the research design, research locale, study participants, research instrument, scoring procedures, data gathering procedure, and the statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study utilized a quasi-experimental research design. The research design compares two groups of respondents, the performance of learners exposed to online collaborative learning and those exposed to online non-collaborative learning. The researcher administered a pre-assessment on both groups to gather quantitative data on their current capacity on the subject enrolled. The researcher grouped the students in the experimental group to implement the Online Collaborative Learning (OCL). Both groups answered the researcher-made exam, the "Team Effectiveness Questionnaire" (TEQ), and the "Motivation to Learn Online Questionnaire" (MLOQ) to assess the effectiveness dimension and student motivation. After the semester, the researcher gave the students the post-assessment to measure their learning for the subject.

Research Locale

The conduct of the study was at San Isidro College (Figure 2), a private educational institution in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. It was established in 1949 by Fr. Joseph Reith, S. J., and initially San Isidro High School.

At present, the college offer programs for students from Kindergarten through College. The institution has the Senior High School offering the Academic and the Technical–Vocational–Livelihood (TVL) tracks. For the college students, available undergraduate programs are in Business Administration and Accountancy, Engineering, Humanities, Information Technology, Health Sciences, and Teacher Education.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Department of Education (DepEd) duly accredited San Isidro College and a member of the Catholic Educational Association of the Philippines (CEAP). Since its establishment, the college has continued to provide its learners with quality Catholic Education; students grow to be competent, nationalistic, and prayerful professionals in their fields.

With the outbreak of COVID-19, the institution implemented distance learning to cater to the learning needs of its enrollees, primarily by virtual instruction. The institution developed learning modules for learners who cannot access the online learning system.

Figure 2. Political Map of Malaybalay City and location of San Isidro College

Participants of the Study

The study participants were college students taking courses in Statistics at San Isidro College. These students were from the second to third years, ages 19 and older. The participants were selected through random sampling from the nine sections taking up a statistics course. There were two sections with forty-seven (47) students that experienced online collaborative learning and another two sections with fifty-one (51) students using a non-collaborative approach to instruction. Both groups had experienced virtual Mathematics with a learner-centered approach to learning.

Sampling Procedure

The respondents of the study were selected using simple random sampling. A total of nine sections took statistics or statistics-related courses, and these sections were heterogeneous. These nine sections that took up the statistics course had their number written on a paper, and the researcher used lottery sampling to select the sections for the study. The researcher chose two groups for the experimental group, with forty-seven (47) students exposed to online collaborative learning. The researcher also chose two classes for the controlled group with fifty-one (51) students who experienced an online non-collaborative approach. The researcher instructed the experimental group to organize themselves with four to five members per group as suggested by Lee and Martin (2017). The relay of instructions is through Google Meet and Facebook Messenger.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in the study is the achievement test on content with a reliability coefficient of 0.754, The Team Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ) with a reliability coefficient of 0.842, and the Motivation to Learn Online Questionnaire (MLOQ) with a reliability coefficient of 0.682. The adoption of the TEQ is from the University of Colorado, London Leadership Academy, and the adoption of the MLOQ is from the master's thesis of Fowler (2017) from the University of Georgia.

Academic Achievement

The content-validated achievement test contains 40 multiple choice questions with ten questions per topic discussed during the duration of the study, namely; 1) measures of central tendency, 2) measures of dispersion, 3) sampling techniques, and 4) hypotheses testing. To determine the validity of the test items, the researcher ensured that the questionnaires had undergone the content and structure review by three experts. The test items were fielded to a Mathematics education consultant, an expert in instructional systems design, and an education research professor. The items were scored 1 for every correct response and 0 otherwise. The researcher pilot-tested the achievement test to the third-year students of San Isidro College and tabulated the gathered data. The Cronbach alpha reliability test was performed on the questionnaire item and obtained a score of 0.754.

The interpretation of the results on the students' exam scores used the scale below, as adopted from the grading system of San Isidro College after the transmutation of the scores;

<u>Range Scale</u>	<u>Level of Achievement</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
96% - 100%	Exemplary	Excellent
93% - 95%	Outstanding	Superior
87% - 92%	Above Average	Very Satisfactory
81% - 86%	Average	Satisfactory
78% - 80%	Fair	Good
75% - 77%	Below Average	Fair
74% and Below	Deficient	Did Not Meet Expectation

Non-Academic Achievement

A. Team Effectiveness

The TEQ examines the team effectiveness in the perspective of eight (8) dimensions, namely; 1) purpose and goals; 2) roles; 3) processes; 4) relationships; 5) intergroup relations; 6) problem solving; 7) passion and commitment; 8) skills and learning. Scores from the TEQ have identified what dimensions of team effectiveness have the highest score and what needs to be improved—using the scores to identify underlying factors that may have influenced the results of the students' rating. The questionnaire contains fifty-six (56) questions answered using the 5-point Likert-type scale (5 – strongly agree, 4 – agree, 3 – neutral, 2 – disagree, and 1 – strongly disagree). Each dimension in the TEQ composes eight statements gaining a maximum rating of 35 and a minimum of 7. The final score is averaged by adding the points of each dimension and dividing it by the total score.

Table 1. Scholarly definition of the eight dimensions of team effectiveness questionnaire.

Survey Tool	Domain Name	Description
TEQ	Purpose and Goals	task's outcome
TEQ	Roles	position taken from specific task
TEQ	Process	goal-directed task work
TEQ	Relationships	connection or interdependence among the students
TEQ	Intergroup Relations	interaction between and among students
TEQ	Problem Solving	analysis and effective solution
TEQ	Passion and Commitments	strength and positive feeling related to identity and performance
TEQ	Skills and Learning	development and understanding of different activities

For every criterion that the respondents would satisfy in each of the five qualities in the TEQ, it was counted as one and multiplied with the assigned corresponding weight as shown below:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Rating</u>	<u>Qualifying Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Agree	Very Low Effectiveness
2	1.81 – 2.60	Agree	Low Effectiveness
3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	No Effect
4	3.41 – 4.20	Disagree	High Effectiveness
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Disagree	Very High Effectiveness

B. Motivation

The MLOQ examines the motivation of the learners to online instruction with the seven factors, namely; 1) intrinsic goal orientation; 2) extrinsic goal orientation; 3) control of learning beliefs; 4) self-efficacy; 5) test anxiety; 6) class contents; and 7) social engagement. The MLOQ was used to identify the students' motivation in the online learning system. The questionnaire contains thirty-seven (37) questions answered using the 5-point Likert-type scale (5 –

strongly agree, 4 – agree, 3 – neutral, 2 – disagree, and 1 – strongly disagree). Each factor in the MLOQ composes four to eight statements gaining a maximum rating of 20 to 40 and a minimum of 4 to 8. The final score is averaged by adding the points of each factor except test anxiety and dividing it by the total score.

Table 2. Scholarly definition of the seven factors of motivation.

Survey Tool	Domain Name	Description
MLOQ	Intrinsic Goal Orientation	internal motivation to learn
MLOQ	Extrinsic Goal Orientation	external motivation to learn
MLOQ	Control of Learning Beliefs	student perception between their behavior and their performance
MLOQ	Self-Efficacy	student's capability to manage and organize situation
MLOQ	Text Anxiety	factors that affect the ability to perform on a test
MLOQ	Class Content	lesson taken in class
MLOQ	Social Engagement	participation in the class or community

For every criterion, except test anxiety, that the respondents would satisfy in each of the five qualities in the MLOQ, it was counted as one and multiplied with the assigned corresponding weight as follow:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Rating</u>	<u>Qualifying Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Highly Unmotivated
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Unmotivated
3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Indifferent
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Motivated
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Motivated

For the criterion on test anxiety that the respondents would satisfy, it was counted as one and multiplied with the assigned corresponding weight as follow:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Rating</u>	<u>Qualifying Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Test Anxiety
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low Test Anxiety
3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Normal Test Anxiety
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Test Anxiety
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Test Anxiety

Data Gathering Procedure

In this study, the researcher used an achievement test on content, the Team Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ), and the Motivation to Learn Online Questionnaire (MOQ). The data collection was collected through Google Classroom and administered using the Google Form and Assignments.

After validating the achievement test on content, the researcher secured written permission from the president and administrator of San Isidro College to conduct the study on the college students. After being given permission, the researcher administered the achievement test as the pre-test for the students to assess the students' initial knowledge on the subject and had one hour to complete the test. The students then answered the TEQ and MLOQ found in the Google Classroom, and the student had one week to complete the questionnaires.

Similarly, after the implementation, the researcher administered the achievement test as the post-test to students to assess what the students learned on the subject and had one hour to complete the test. The students then answered the TEQ and MLOQ found in the Google Classroom, and the student had one week to complete the questionnaires. Data gathered from the TEQ and MLOQ was organized and encoded in statistical software. Due to data privacy, the researcher asked permission from the student to make use of the conversation in the group chat. Only one group responded that they would allow making use of their conversation.

Management of Class

OCL follows a structured approach to its implementation. The instructor introduced the concepts to the learners, and the students developed the idea by divergent thinking and communication through social media platforms with the teachers' facilitation. The instructor will guide the students and provide the appropriate feedback as students compare and argue about their ideas to help them categorize their thoughts. As the students end their discussion, they will agree to finalize their concepts and their learning tasks.

OCL discussions are shorter to help facilitate the collaboration process of the students, and the time is only for general instruction and a brief introduction to the topic. The OCL class uses the rest of the time to generate an idea and discuss it before organizing their concept. At the end of the learning process, the OCL group needs to synthesize their overall concept discussion to answer their class tasks.

Non-OCL classes are longer to help students facilitate their learning and answer their questions while in class. The idea generation and organization happen in the online platforms and will end with the class wrapping things up by sharing their overall learning with the class. The teacher facilitates both OCL and non-OCL discussions. OCL is an effective method as it addresses the heterogeneity of the section with its flexible and self-paced approach.

Statistical Techniques

The data were coded and processed using statistical software. All the treatments have a 5% or 0.05 level of significance.

To answer questions 1, 2, and 3, the researcher used descriptive statistics to obtain the mean and standard deviation of the students' responses.

To answer questions 4, 5, and 6, the researcher used the ANCOVA to compare the pre-test and post-test scores, the rating on motivation, and the effectiveness rating of the students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The content of this chapter is with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data to determine the students' academic achievement and motivation of virtual Mathematics via online collaborative learning. The organization of the discussion of the tables provides a straightforward analysis of the data. The order of presentation follows the statement of the problem set in the study.

Academic Achievement of the Students Exposed to OCL and Non-OCL Groups

Table 3 presents the students' academic achievement levels in their pre-test. The table also displays frequency, qualitative interpretation, and percentage of the students exposed to OCL and non-OCL.

Table 3. Level of students' academic achievement in the pre-test

RANGE	Level of Achievement	GROUP				Quantitative Interpretation
		OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51		
		f	%	f	%	
96% - 100%	Exemplary	0	0	0	0	Excellent
93% - 95%	Outstanding	0	0	0	0	Superior
87% - 92%	Above Average	0	0	0	0	Very Satisfactory
81% - 86%	Average	0	0	0	0	Satisfactory
78% - 80%	Fair	3	6	2	4	Good
75% - 77%	Below Average	0	0	2	4	Fair
74% and Below		44	94	47	92	Did Not Meet Expectation
Mean Percentage Score (MPS)		46		48		
Qualitative Interpretation (QI)		Did Not Meet Expectation		Did Not Meet Expectation		

Table 3 reflects that the OCL group has a mean score of 18.32 and a mean percentage score of 46%, which shows that the student's score is

deficient, implying that the students did not meet the expectation. The non-OCL group has a mean score of 19.20 and a mean percentage score of 48%, which shows that the student's score is at the deficient level, which implies that the students did not meet the expectation. According to table 3, both groups performed the same in the achievement test on the content.

Reyes-Chua et al. (2020) support the findings that the students' scores did not meet the expectation and signify a deficient performance or deficiency in understanding. As expected, the pre-test result did not meet the expectations because the learners were not well-versed with the concepts (Kelly, 2019; Bird, Castleman, Lohner, 2020; Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020). Moreover, the pre-test often shows low performance since many of the learners are only starting and do not possess or lack the necessary knowledge to answer the questions (Bates, 2014; Eric, 2015; Racheva, 2017; Ahn and Edwin, 2018; Lai, Wen, Gao, and Lin, 2020).

Table 4 presents the students' academic achievement level in their post-test. The table also displays frequency, qualitative interpretation, and percentage of the students exposed to OCL and non-OCL.

Table 4. Level of students' academic achievement in the post-test

RANGE	Level of Achievement	GROUP				Quantitative Interpretation
		OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51		
		f	%	f	%	
96% - 100%	Exemplary	7	15	4	8	Excellent
93% - 95%	Outstanding	9	19	6	12	Superior
87% - 92%	Above Average	8	17	8	15	Very Satisfactory
81% - 86%	Average	12	26	6	12	Satisfactory
78% - 80%	Fair	5	11	6	12	Good
75% - 77%	Below Average	2	4	1	2	Fair
74% and Below		4	8	20	39	Did Not Meet Expectation
Mean Percentage Score (MPS)		87		75		
Qualitative Interpretation (QI)		Very Satisfactory		Fair		

Table 4 reflects the level of academic achievement of the students from the post-test result. The OCL group has a mean score of 34.64 and a mean

percentage score of 87%, which shows that the student's score is at the above-average level, indicating that the student's performance is very satisfactory. On the other hand, the non-OCL group had a mean score of 30.10 and a mean percentage score of 75%, which shows that the student's score is below average, indicating that the student's performance is fair.

As shown in table 3, the mean score of the students in the 40-item teacher-made test in the OCL and non-OCL groups shows that they belong to the deficient level that indicates the students did not meet expectations in Statistics. Moreover, as shown in table 4, the mean scores of both groups improved. The mean score of the students in the OCL group shows a "very satisfactory" result, and the students in the non-OCL group indicate a "fair" result. The higher achievement of the OCL group is due to the collaboration between the members and the feedbacking peer system where students can help each other understand the material and lesson. The OCL has encouraged the students' interaction, promoting feedbacking and peer support that helps students learn online.

The study of Lai, Wen, Gao, and Lin (2020) supports this result stating, that with the exposure of two groups to different teaching environments, the content knowledge increases as indicated in the learners' post-test scores after the treatment. The increase in the academic achievement of the students' attributed to the asynchronous nature and flexible instruction of online learning (Shang and Chen, 2018; Hernandez et al., 2019; Al-Nofaie, 2020; Andrade, Miller, Kunz and Ratliff, 2020; Paulsen and McCormick, 2020). Furthermore, the ease of use of technology and the materials available on the internet and classroom can contribute to the students learning (Deniz and Simsek, 2015; Huang, Kellert and Manouchehri, 2015; Kim and Park, 2018; Figg and Khirwadkar, 2020).

Motivation of Students in OCL and non-OCL Groups

Intrinsic Goal Orientation

Table 5 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning the intrinsic goal orientation and presents the degree of motivation for the students to learn online.

Table 5. Students' mean score on motivation to learn online in relation to Intrinsic Goal Orientation

INTRINSIC GOAL ORIENTATION	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I prefer material that arouses my curiosity, even if it's difficult to learn.	4.40	Highly Motivated	3.65	Motivated
2. The most satisfying thing for me is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible.	4.40	Highly Motivated	3.86	Motivated
3. I prefer material that really challenges me, so I can learn new things.	4.28	Highly Motivated	3.86	Motivated
4. I choose assignments that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade.	4.19	Motivated	3.71	Motivated
OVERALL MEAN	4.32	Highly Motivated	3.77	Motivated

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.32, indicating that the learners are highly intrinsically motivated to learn. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.77, which indicates that the learners of the group are intrinsically motivated to learn. The factors affecting the high intrinsic motivation of the students in the OCL group are the quality of the material that challenges the students to understand the materials. The factor affecting the students' motivation in the non-OCL group is the overall quality of learning, even if good grades are not guaranteed. The high intrinsic motivation

of the OCL group is due to the feedback and support of the members that can contribute to the individuals' intrinsic motivation.

The intrinsic motivation of the students can be attributed to their willingness to learn and the drive to continue with educating themselves, even in an online setting (Bonito; 2013; Al-Nofaie, 2020; Fernando, Thiry, Queiroz, Fernandes, 2020; Sze, 2020; Chua, 2021). Aduayi-Akue et al. (2017) and Gocotano et al. (2021) support the result where learners control their motivation to learn, both gaining or losing motivation. Additionally, learners are more motivated to learn in an online setting because of the flexibility, and the students control their own time to learn (Fowler, 2017; Avila et al., 2020; Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020; Estira, 2020; Malinauska and Pozeriene, 2020).

Extrinsic Goal Orientation

Table 6 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning extrinsic goal orientation and the degree of motivation for extrinsic goal orientation.

Table 6. Students' mean score on motivation to learn online in relation to Extrinsic Goal Orientation

EXTRINSIC GOAL ORIENTATION	GROUP			
	Mean	OCL n=47 Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	non-OCL n=51 Qualitative Interpretation
1. Getting a good grade is the most satisfying thing for me.	4.55	Highly Motivated	4.14	Motivated
2. The most important thing for me is to improve my overall grade point average, so my concern is getting a good grade.	4.51	Highly Motivated	3.98	Motivated
3. I want to do well in my classes because it's important to show my ability to my family, friends, employer, or others.	4.30	Highly Motivated	3.86	Motivated
4. I want to get better grades than most of the other students in my classes.	3.79	Motivated	3.37	Indifferent
OVERALL MEAN	4.29	Highly Motivated	3.84	Motivated

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.29, indicating that the learners are extrinsically motivated to learn. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.84, which indicates that the learners are motivated extrinsically to learn. The factors affecting the high extrinsic motivation of the OCL group and the extrinsic motivation of the non-OCL group are the students' desire to get good grades and to show their skill and ability to the class. The high extrinsic motivation of the OCL group is due to the group's goal to achieve good grades and the determination to attain the group's goal.

The extrinsic motivation of the students can be attributed to the grades that they received at the end of the term, which motivates them to do good in their classes and learn to improve their academic standing (Elizabeth and John,

2012; Bonito, 2013; Magen-Nagar and Shonfeld, 2018; Avila et al., 2020). Learners identify their reasons to learn because of a possible reward or receive something at the end of their endeavor, thus creating an external drive to accomplish a task or activity (Aduayu-Akue et al., 2017; Estira, 2020). Furthermore, Fowler (2017) and Lee and Martin (2017) detailed that online learning creates multiple opportunities for students to motivate themselves extrinsically. Learners look for opportunities to present their skills to others and gain good grades because of their efforts (Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021; Oraif and Elyas, 2021).

Control of Learning Beliefs

Table 7 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning learners' ability to control their learning beliefs and presents the degree of motivation to control the students' learning behavior.

Table 7. Students' mean score on motivation to learn online in relation to Control of Learning Beliefs

CONTROL OF LEARNING BELIEFS	GROUP			
	Mean	OCL n=47 Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	non-OCL n=51 Qualitative Interpretation
1. If I study in appropriate ways, then I'll be able to learn the material.	4.57	Highly Motivated	3.90	Motivated
2. If I try hard enough, then I'll understand the material presented.	4.51	Highly Motivated	3.78	Motivated
3. It's my own fault if I don't learn the material taught.	4.19	Motivated	3.90	Motivated
4. If I don't understand the material presented, it's because I didn't try hard enough.	3.94	Motivated	3.84	Motivated
OVERALL MEAN	4.30	Highly Motivated	3.86	Motivated

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.30, which indicates that the learners can control their learning beliefs and are highly motivated to learn. Similarly, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.86, which indicates that the learners can control their learning beliefs and are motivated to learn. The factor affecting the high control of learning beliefs of the OCL group and the control of the non-OCL group is the students' determination to study hard and study habits. However, their beliefs are affected by their personal beliefs and the lack of determination to study complex materials. The high control of learning beliefs of the OCL group is due to the groups' support system where the students can validate and compare their belief of learning and make the changes to improve themselves through peer support.

The learners' capacity to control their learning beliefs is linked to online classrooms' opportunity to work in a self-paced manner and would prompt the learners to adjust to their learning needs (Bates, 2014; Eric, 2015; Racheva, 2017; Ahn and Edwin, 2018; Tamm, 2020b). Since learners control their learning, they can go through the lessons in a self-paced approach and internalize them properly (Avila et al., 2020; Estira, 2020). Furthermore, online learning can promote students' positive beliefs and regulate them according to their learning subject (Bonito, 2013; Harandi, 2015; Fowler; 2017; Stockleben et al., 2017).

Self-Efficacy

Table 8 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning learners' self-efficacy and presents the degree of motivation for the students' self-efficacy to learn online.

Table 8. Students' mean score on motivation to learn online in relation to Self-Efficacy.

SELF-EFFICACY	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I expect to do well.	4.19	Motivated	3.96	Motivated
2. Considering the difficulty of the classes, the teachers, and my skills, I think I can do well.	4.19	Motivated	3.69	Motivated
3. I'm confident I can learn the basic concepts that are being taught.	4.17	Motivated	3.76	Motivated
4. I'm confident I can do an excellent job on assignments and tests.	4.02	Motivated	3.78	Motivated
5. I'm certain I can master the skills being taught.	4.00	Motivated	3.65	Motivated
6. I believe I'll receive excellent grades in my classes.	3.98	Motivated	3.80	Motivated
7. I'm certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the readings.	3.79	Motivated	3.33	Indifferent
8. I'm confident I can understand the most complex material presented by the instructor.	3.89	Motivated	3.51	Motivated
OVERALL MEAN	4.03	Motivated	3.69	Motivated

The OCL group overall mean of 4.03, which indicates that the learners are motivated to learn due to high self-efficacy. While the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.69, indicating that the learners are motivated to learn due to high self-efficacy. The factor affecting the self-efficacy of both the OCL and the non-OCL group are the students' confidence in their skills and abilities to learn the materials given and the expectation to get good grades.

The high self-efficacy of the student is due to the flexible nature of online learning, which boosts students' efficacy in-class activities and tests (Fowler, 2017; Ucar and Goksel, 2020). The result in table 8 displays that both groups are motivated to learn in an online setting because of the certainty and feeling of confidence (Kim and Frick, 2011; Bonito 2013; Gocotano et al., 2021). Furthermore, easy access to information and communication can improve students' self-efficacy, which boosts their belief in themselves (Harandi, 2015; Condict, 2016; Avila et al., 2020; Avila, Maria and Genio, 2020; Estira, 2020).

Test Anxiety

Table 9 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning test anxiety and presents the degree of test anxiety of the students in an online platform.

Table 9. Students' mean score on motivation to learn online in relation to Test Anxiety

TEST ANXIETY	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I have an uneasy, upset feeling when I take exams.	2.26	Low Test Anxiety	3.65	High Test Anxiety
2. When taking exams, I feel my heart beating fast.	2.23	Low Test Anxiety	3.73	High Test Anxiety
3. When I take tests, I think of the consequences of failing.	2.23	Low Test Anxiety	3.69	High Test Anxiety
4. When I take tests, I think about items on other parts of the tests I can't answer.	2.21	Low Test Anxiety	3.69	High Test Anxiety
5. When I take tests, I think about how poorly I'm doing compared with other students.	2.17	Low Test Anxiety	4.18	High Test Anxiety
OVERALL MEAN	2.22	Low Test Anxiety	3.78	High Test Anxiety

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 2.22, which indicates that the learners possess low-test anxiety. In contrast, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.78, indicating that the learners possess high test anxiety. The low-test anxiety of the OCL group is due to the students' confidence when taking the test and in themselves. The high-test anxiety of the non-OCL group is due to the students feeling of unease and nervousness when taking the test and the fear of failing. Due to the group support when making sense of the materials and notes of the OCL group, each member is confident in taking their exams and has low test anxiety.

The study of Elizabeth and John (2012) supports the result of the OCL group, where learners are more confident with themselves in taking the test when they are in a social learning environment and promote learning and retention. Also, online collaboration can foster student learning because of support from members and the feedback mechanisms that help correct faulty information (Harasim, 2012). The study by Bonito (2013) and Mese and Sevilen (2021) supports the result of the non-OCL group, where high test anxiety results from the lack of social interaction among students. This social isolation can increase the anxiety of a student, especially during exams (Fowler, 2017; Tamm, 2020a).

Students feel that they cannot do well in a test because they are unsure of themselves or the information they have studied or researched, thus building anxiety (Aduayi-Akue et al., 2017). Additionally, many textbook activities are available on the internet through different websites and are accessible by the student (Subin, 2021). They were prompting students to search for the answers to make their work easier and lessen their feeling overwhelmed by their academic workload (Schaffhauser, 2020; Rowan and Murray, 2021; Magsabol, 2021).

Class Content

Table 10 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning class content and presents the degree of motivation for the students learning online.

Table 10. Students' mean score on motivation to learn online in relation to Class Content

CLASS CONTENT	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I think my online classes are challenging.	4.40	Highly Motivated	3.92	Motivated
2. I have control over my learning process.	4.09	Motivated	3.53	Motivated
3. I enjoy online classes.	3.85	Motivated	3.41	Motivated
4. I learn the content well in online classes.	3.81	Motivated	3.45	Motivated
5. I choose online classes because they fit my personal schedule.	3.62	Motivated	3.51	Motivated
6. Classes are easy for me.	3.43	Motivated	3.10	Indifferent
7. Cheating on online tests is easy.	3.38	Motivated	3.31	Indifferent
OVERALL MEAN	3.80	Motivated	3.46	Motivated

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.80, which indicates that the learners are motivated to learn the class content. The non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.46, which indicates that the learners are motivated to learn the class content. Students' motivation in the class content in both OCL and non-OCL groups is due to the control the learners have on their learning, the flexible nature of online classes and activities, and the enjoyment they experience in going through the materials. Nevertheless, the ease of cheating in online activities and the challenges some students face are factors to consider in their experience in learning the class content.

The increase in motivation to learn the class content is due to multiple sources of information available for the student, and this can be a source of interest to learn for many (Chyung, Moll, and Berg, 2010; Bonitio, 2013; Huang, Kellert, and Manouchehri, 2015; Figg and Khirwadkar, 2020). Furthermore, online materials are readily available for students who are not satisfied with the materials given by the instructor, the readily available materials can increase interest and motivate students to learn on their own while referencing the provided material (Fowler, 2017; Makel et al., 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021). Counter-intuitively, table 10's result on the motivation to cheat is also a driving factor for students to refer to online materials and make use of the materials to

cheat in exams (Chyung, Moll, and Berg, 2010; Tamma, 2020; Esrita, 2020; Ucak and Goksel, 2020).

Social Engagement

Table 11 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning social engagement and presents the degree of motivation considering the social engagement of students in an online classroom.

Table 11. Students' mean score on motivation to learn online in relation to Social Engagement

SOCIAL ENGAGEMENT	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I pay attention in online classes.	4.06	Motivated	3.63	Motivated
2. I feel like I can freely communicate with the instructor in online classes.	3.79	Motivated	3.88	Motivated
3. I enjoy online class discussions.	3.57	Motivated	3.57	Motivated
4. I feel like I can freely communicate with other students in online classes.	3.55	Motivated	3.45	Motivated
5. I feel "disconnected" from my teacher and fellow students in classes.	3.34	Indifferent	3.67	Motivated
OVERALL MEAN	3.66	Motivated	3.64	Motivated

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.66, which indicates that the learners are motivated in social engagement. The non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.64, which indicates that the learners are motivated in social engagement. The student's social engagement in both OCL and non-OCL groups is due to their attention to class, communication between the faculty and fellow students, and the engagement promotes students' enjoyment in their classes, but the disconnect that some experience may affect the overall experience.

The study of Pando (2018) and Gocotano (2021) supports the result of table 11, which claimed that students would naturally interact with one another and find ways to do so. Learners who have a hard time with their materials or instruction ask their peers or even their instructor for assistance (Bonito, 2013; Fowler, 2017; Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020). The devices and internet aid the students' motivation to learn in online instruction, with the guidance of the instructor or their peers (Huang, Kellert, and Manouchehri, 2015; Deniz and Simsek, 2015; Avila et al., 2020; Estira, 2020). However, the low mean scores of the student can also be the cause of social isolation or the inhibition to reach out and ask for help from their peers or instructors (Tucker et al., 2017; Tamma, 2020; Mese and Sevilen, 2021).

Effectiveness of Students in OCL and non-OCL Groups

Purpose and Goals

Table 12 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning purpose and goals and presents the extent of effectiveness of purpose and goals of the students to learn online.

Table 12. Students' mean score in Effectiveness in relation to Purpose and Goals

PURPOSE AND GOALS	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. We make sure our work helps the organization achieve its goals.	4.60	Very High Effectiveness	3.71	High Effectiveness
2. The mission and goals of my team are well aligned with the organization's mission and goals.	4.60	Very High Effectiveness	3.75	High Effectiveness
3. Our team has a meaningful, shared purpose.	4.53	Very High Effectiveness	3.57	High Effectiveness
4. We are strongly committed to a shared mission.	4.49	Very High Effectiveness	3.59	High Effectiveness
5. We consistently produce strong, measurable results.	4.49	Very High Effectiveness	3.49	High Effectiveness
6. We focus on big-picture strategic issues as much as on day-to-day activities.	4.47	Very High Effectiveness	3.55	High Effectiveness
7. We set and meet challenging goals.	4.47	Very High Effectiveness	3.49	High Effectiveness
OVERALL MEAN	4.52	Very High Effectiveness	3.59	High Effectiveness

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.52, which indicates that the learners have very high effectiveness in purpose and goals. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.59, which indicates that the learners have high effectiveness in purpose and goals. The very high effectiveness on the purpose and goals of the OCL group is due to the group's goal to align their goals to the lesson and attain a meaningful purpose with their experience through the groups' commitment. At the same time, the high effectiveness on purpose and goals of the non-OLC group is due to the individuals' desire to attain their learning goals and give their efforts and commitment to learn and produce an outcome in class.

The study of Harasim (2012) and Raymundo (2020) further supports the result that online learning helps students set the purpose of their learning and establish a goal they want to attain at the end of the term. In an online class, establishing the goal of learning is essential, online learning makes this happen

because of its flexible nature, and students can easily set and identify the goals of their learning (Nguyen, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Lee and Martin, 2017; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Dizon, 2020). Moreover, online learning has a positive influence on goal setting because the platform does not restrict the students and encourages them to set and identify their goals, with the guidance of the instructor (Deniz and Simsek, 2015; Du et al., 2018; Kim and Park, 2018; Sze, 2020).

Role

Table 13 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning the role and presents the extent of effectiveness of roles of the students to learn online.

Table 13. Students' mean score in Effectiveness in relation to Roles

ROLES	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Team members understand one another's roles.	4.62	Very High Effectiveness	3.78	High Effectiveness
2. Everyone values what each member contributes to the team.	4.60	Very High Effectiveness	3.80	High Effectiveness
3. When team members' roles change, specific plans are implemented to help them assume their new responsibilities.	4.53	Very High Effectiveness	3.76	High Effectiveness
4. Team members clearly understand their roles.	4.49	Very High Effectiveness	3.65	High Effectiveness
5. When an individual's role changes, an intentional effort is made to clarify it for everyone on the team.	4.49	Very High Effectiveness	3.71	High Effectiveness
6. Team members avoid duplication of effort and make sure they are clear about who is doing what.	4.47	Very High Effectiveness	3.71	High Effectiveness
7. Overlapping or shared tasks and responsibilities do not create problems for team members.	4.32	Very High Effectiveness	3.33	High Effectiveness
OVERALL MEAN	4.50	Very High Effectiveness	3.68	High Effectiveness

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.50, which indicates that the learners have very high effectiveness in their roles in the group. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.68, which indicates that the learners have high effectiveness in their roles in class. The very high effectiveness of roles of the OCL group in role designation is due to the respect and understanding of their roles to the group for the group's overall efficiency. The OCL group also divides their work equally and respects the roles of each member. At the same time, the high effectiveness of the non-OLC group's roles in learning is due to the flexible nature of each individual and understanding the role to do as a student.

Harasim (2012) and Chua (2021) support the result that students self-identify their roles in learning even if the teacher does not assign them. Online learning is a self-directed approach to education, where students subconsciously assign their roles for them, and easy for them to realize what they need to do (Nguyen, 2015; Kim and Park, 2018; Shang and Chen, 2018; Dizon, 2020; Raymundo, 2020). Furthermore, the effectiveness of both groups in identifying their roles is due to the self-paced nature of online learning and the instructions that facilitate learning (Dreamson, 2016; Akhter and Mahmood, 2018; Lam and Kapur, 2018; Andrade, Miller, Kunz, and Ratliff, 2020).

Team Process

Table 14 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning team process and presents the extent of effectiveness of the students learning online.

Table 14. Students' mean score in Effectiveness in relation to Process

PROCESS	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. When we choose consensus decision-making, we do it effectively.	4.53	Very High Effectiveness	3.76	High Effectiveness
2. Team problem solving results in effective solutions.	4.43	Very High Effectiveness	3.88	High Effectiveness
3. Group meetings are very productive.	4.40	Very High Effectiveness	3.68	High Effectiveness
4. Our team has mechanisms in place to monitor its results.	4.38	Very High Effectiveness	3.55	High Effectiveness
5. Our team works with a great deal of flexibility so that we can adapt to changing needs.	4.38	Very High Effectiveness	3.78	High Effectiveness
6. People on my team are rewarded for being team players.	4.34	Very High Effectiveness	3.61	High Effectiveness
7. We address and resolve issues quickly.	4.30	Very High Effectiveness	3.57	High Effectiveness
OVERALL MEAN	4.40	Very High Effectiveness	3.72	High Effectiveness

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.40, indicating that the learners are very effective in their process. The non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.72, which indicates that the learners have high effectiveness in the process. The very high effectiveness of the process of the OCL group is due to the groups' division of tasks and arriving at a feasible solution, and making the needed decision making. The group's efforts are to adapt to the changes and resolve the issues of the group quickly. The high effectiveness of the process of the non-OCL group is due to the individuals' productive nature and adaptability to the changes in the lessons and resolve the issues they have quickly.

The effectiveness of the students' process links to the availability of communication and materials, which aids the student to facilitate their learning and even extent to others if need be (Gutierrez, 2013; Stephan, 2014; Magen-Nagar and Shonfeld, 2018). The study of Hammond (2017) supports the result

that learners can process the information given to them because of the free-range availability of information and the flexibility of online learning, making learners more active in the process rather than passive receivers of information. Additionally, with the facilitation of their learning, students can be more confident in the learning process that they are engaged in or are more active when making decisions (Harasim, 2012; Nguyen, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Dizon, 2020; Raymundo, 2020).

Relationships

Table 15 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning relationships and presents the extent of effectiveness of relationships of the students to learn online.

Table 15. Students' mean score in Effectiveness in relation to Relationships

RELATIONSHIPS	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Team members help one another deal with problems or resolve issues	4.68	Very High Effectiveness	3.80	High Effectiveness
2. Team members appreciate one another's unique capabilities.	4.62	Very High Effectiveness	4.02	High Effectiveness
3. Team members are effective listeners.	4.62	Very High Effectiveness	3.82	High Effectiveness
4. Members of our team trust each other.	4.66	Very High Effectiveness	3.80	High Effectiveness
5. Team members display high levels of cooperation and mutual support.	4.66	Very High Effectiveness	3.78	High Effectiveness
6. Communication in our group is open and honest.	4.60	Very High Effectiveness	3.75	High Effectiveness
7. We are able to work through differences of opinion without damaging relationships.	4.60	Very High Effectiveness	3.73	High Effectiveness
OVERALL MEAN	4.63	Very High Effectiveness	3.82	High Effectiveness

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.63, which indicates that the learners have a very high effectiveness in their relationships with other groups and students. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.82, which indicates that the learners have high effectiveness in their relationships with other students. The very high effectiveness of the OCL group relationships is due to the teamwork and peer support that the students display to one another and cooperate to attain the group goal. The high effectiveness of the non-OCL group relationships is due to students' trust with the instruction and materials and the open communication between the student and the instructor.

The effectiveness of the relationships among students is due to the social media platforms that they can access, and this, in turn, aids them to communicate with one another (Lee and Martin, 2012; Bates 2014; Eric, 2015; Stockleben et al., 2017; Du et al., 2018; Dizon, 2020). The study of Makel et al. (2020) supports the result, which states that the support of peers can help learners overcome challenges in an online setting and increase the effectiveness of learning. Furthermore, online platforms can help facilitate learning by the healthy exchange of information and easy access to communicate with one another (Matranga and Koku, 2015; Condict, 2016; Dreamson, 2016; Raymundo, 2020).

Intergroup Relations

Table 16 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning intergroup relations and presents the extent of effectiveness of the students to learn online.

Table 16. Students' mean score in Effectiveness in relation to Intergroup Relations

INTERGROUP RELATIONS	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. We are able to resolve conflicts with other teams collaboratively.	4.32	Very High Effectiveness	3.78	High Effectiveness
2. We communicate effectively with other groups.	4.32	Very High Effectiveness	3.65	High Effectiveness
3. We seek to arrange our priorities to meet the needs of other work groups.	4.23	Very High Effectiveness	3.75	High Effectiveness
4. Our collaborations with other teams are productive, worthwhile, and yield good results.	4.21	Very High Effectiveness	3.73	High Effectiveness
5. Our team has established trusting and supportive relationships with other teams.	4.19	High Effectiveness	3.96	High Effectiveness
6. The goals of our group support those of other groups.	4.19	High Effectiveness	3.76	High Effectiveness
7. We work toward integrating our plans with those of other work groups.	4.11	High Effectiveness	3.59	High Effectiveness
OVERALL MEAN	4.23	Very High Effectiveness	3.75	High Effectiveness

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.22, which indicates that the learners have very high effectiveness concerning their relationship with other groups and individuals. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.75, which indicates that the learners have high effectiveness regarding their relation to other individuals. The very high effectiveness on intergroup relations of the OCL group is due to the peer support and relation between the other groups that help them set priorities and resolve the conflict between other groups. The high effectiveness on intergroup relations of the non-OCL group is due to the relationship that each individual has with others and the desire to resolve the conflict between other classmates also to improve the relationship between others.

The effectiveness of the relationship among students can be due to their common interests and goals. These shared interests and goals urge them to work together or assist one another for the benefit of both parties (Bates 2014; Eric, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Tan and Vicente, 2019). This result supports the study of Harasim (2012) and Balsler, Grabau, Knieess, and Page (2018) that to succeed in an online platform, communication with other learners is a crucial aspect. The result implies that one student's success is the success of the entire class. Additionally, students are naturally interactive and seek other learners to assist them if they need help understanding or have clarification that they cannot ask from their instructor (Deniz and Simsek, 2015; Matranga and Koku, 2015; Dizon, 2020). The online platform used for instruction can help facilitate the healthy exchange of information between students and provide a monitoring system for students learning (Stockleben et al., 2017; Raymundo, 2020).

Problem Solving

Table 17 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning problem-solving and presents the extent of effectiveness of the students learning online.

Table 17. Students' mean score in Effectiveness in relation to Problem Solving

PROBLEM SOLVING	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Team members take personal responsibility for the effectiveness of our team.	4.51	Very High Effectiveness	3.67	High Effectiveness
2. Team members consider how their actions will impact others when deciding what to do.	4.49	Very High Effectiveness	3.92	High Effectiveness
3. Team members are sure about what is expected of them and take pride in a job well done.	4.45	Very High Effectiveness	3.78	High Effectiveness
4. Team members take initiative to resolve issues between themselves without involving the team leader.	4.40	Very High Effectiveness	3.63	High Effectiveness
5. Team members maintain a can-do approach when they encounter frustrating situations.	4.38	Very High Effectiveness	3.61	High Effectiveness
6. Team members seek and give each other constructive feedback.	4.34	Very High Effectiveness	3.63	High Effectiveness
7. We spend very little time complaining about things we cannot control.	4.21	Very High Effectiveness	3.49	High Effectiveness
OVERALL MEAN	4.40	Very High Effectiveness	3.68	High Effectiveness

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.40, which indicates that the learners have very high effectiveness in problem-solving. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.68, which indicates that the learners have high effectiveness in problem-solving. The very high effectiveness on problem-solving of the OCL group is due to the roles that each member has and the personal responsibility they share with the group. The OCL group can also provide peer feedback on the work of the other members that help them improve their performance. The high effectiveness of the non-OCL group is due to the self-initiative of the students to arrive at a feasible and

viable solution and the individual's ability to work under pressure to accomplish a learning task.

The study of Harasim (2012) and Raymundo (2020) supports the result that learners can become effective problem solvers in an online setting because they are exposed to and molded to adapt to the changes they experience. Exposure to different information is encouraged in the online learning system to identify important information beneficial to their learning (Nguyen, 2015; Tucker et al., 2017; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Dizon, 2020; Chua, 2021). In addition, online learning can cultivate multiple skills, i.e., problem-solving, to aid the learners and even encourage them to work with other individuals even further to develop the skill (Purcell, Buchanan, and Friedrich, 2013; Eric, 2015; Condict; 2016; Reyes-Chua et al., 2020).

Passion and Commitment

Table 18 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning passion and commitment and presents the extent of effectiveness of the students learning online.

Table 18. Students' mean score in Effectiveness in relation to Passion and Commitment

PASSION AND COMMITMENT	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Working on our team inspires people to do their best.	4.49	Very High Effectiveness	4.00	High Effectiveness
2. My team has a strong sense of accomplishment relative to our work.	4.49	Very High Effectiveness	3.86	High Effectiveness
3. My team is proud of its accomplishments and optimistic about the future.	4.49	Very High Effectiveness	3.80	High Effectiveness
4. As a team, we work to attract and retain top performers.	4.47	Very High Effectiveness	3.67	High Effectiveness
5. People are proud to be part of our team.	4.45	Very High Effectiveness	3.76	High Effectiveness
6. Our team is excited about the contribution it is making to the organization's competitive viability.	4.38	Very High Effectiveness	3.75	High Effectiveness
7. Team members frequently go beyond what is required and do not hesitate to take initiative.	4.36	Very High Effectiveness	3.82	High Effectiveness
OVERALL MEAN	4.45	Very High Effectiveness	3.81	High Effectiveness

The OCL group has an overall means core of 4.45, which indicates that the learners have very high effectiveness in their passion and commitment to their learning and team. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.81, which indicates that the learners have high effectiveness in their passion and commitment to their learning and team. The very high effectiveness on passion and commitment of the OCL group is due to the inspiration that each member can give to each other to accomplish work and go beyond what is asked of them. The OCL group is optimistic about doing and finishing their work and is excited to do the work. The high effectiveness of the non-OCL group's passion and commitment is due to each individual's inspiration to finish the work, accomplish their work on time, and even go beyond what is asked.

This result supports the study of Hammond (2017) and Tarum (2019), stating that learners are more passionate about their work in an online setting due to the flexibility offered in an online class. Learners are empowered and control their learning, motivating them to do their best. The online classroom also promotes commitment to learning among the student because they are no longer pressured to accomplish their task in the classroom but rather in the comforts of their homes (Elizabeth and John, 2012; Nguyen, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Maxwell, Smoker, and Stites-Doe, 2018; Raymundo, 2020). Additionally, the result goes against the study of Bird, Castleman, and Ratliff (2020), Rowan and Murray (2021), and Magsabol (2021) claiming that students would lose interest in classes and would be less effective in their performance.

Skills and Learning

Table 19 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation in motivation to learn online concerning skills and learning and presents the extent of effectiveness of the students learning online.

Table 19. Students' mean score in Effectiveness in relation to Skill and Learning

SKILLS AND LEARNING	GROUP			
	OCL n=47		non-OCL n=51	
	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Team members embrace continuous improvement as a way of life.	4.60	Very High Effectiveness	3.92	High Effectiveness
2. We have the skills we need to do our jobs effectively.	4.53	Very High Effectiveness	3.80	High Effectiveness
3. We always ask ourselves, "How can we do better tomorrow what we did today?"	4.47	Very High Effectiveness	3.88	High Effectiveness
4. We view everything, even mistakes, as opportunities for learning and growth.	4.47	Very High Effectiveness	3.75	High Effectiveness
5. Team members work to ensure we are using best practice methods.	4.47	Very High Effectiveness	4.02	High Effectiveness
6. As a team, we are continually working to improve cycle time, speed to market, customer responsiveness, or other key performance indicators.	4.38	Very High Effectiveness	3.67	High Effectiveness
7. We use various forms of training to keep our skills up-to-date.	4.34	Very High Effectiveness	3.98	High Effectiveness
OVERALL MEAN	4.47	Very High Effectiveness	3.86	High Effectiveness

The OCL group has an overall mean score of 4.47, which indicates that the learners have very high effectiveness in developing their skills and learning. In comparison, the non-OCL group has an overall mean score of 3.86, which indicates that the learners have high effectiveness in developing their skills and learning. The very high effectiveness on skills and learning of the OCL group is due to the groups' pursuit for continuous improvement and using the best practices to maximize their time and effort. The high effectiveness of the non-OCL group skills and learning is due to the student's opportunistic nature and conducting self-check on their improvement to facilitate their development in class.

The study of Purcell, Buchanan, and Friedrich (2013) and Raymundo (2020) supports the result by affirming that online learning can contribute to developing the students' skills and improving their learning. When encountering a challenging situation or a complicated topic, students are well versed in researching the information that would benefit them or that would inform them, and this promotes the effectiveness of learning in the online setting (Nguyen, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Hammond, 2017; Abudmaid, 2020). Furthermore, online learning can improve students' skills, especially in material validation. The online platform creates an avenue for learners to explore and expand their understanding (Kim and Park, 2018; Shang and Chen, 2018; Dizon, 2020; Figg, Khirwadkar, and Welbourn, 2020; Reiten, 2020).

Difference on the Academic Achievement of Students Exposed to OCL and Non-OCL

Table 20 presents the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of pre-test and post-test results between interventions.

Table 20. Comparison of students' academic performance between groups

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	34.64	3.460		
Non-OCL	51	30.10	6.854		
Total	98	32.28	5.925		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	480.340	1	480.340	16.216	0.000**
Pre-test	87.401	1	87.401	2.951	0.089
Error	2813.960	95			
TOTAL	105493.00	98			

Note:** – Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 20, the pre-test was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 16.216 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that the

academic achievement of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning are the same, is rejected.

The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 34.64 has higher test scores than the non-OCL group with a mean of 30.10, which would mean further that there is a significant difference found in their academic performance based on the post-test result. Notice in Table 3 that the non-OCL group student performed better than the OCL group. Table 4 depicts that the students in the OCL group now performed better than the non-OCL group.

The study of Harasim (2012) and Magen-Nagar and Shonfeld (2018) further supports the impact of online collaborative learning that students perceive the OCL approach as a positive experience. Students believe that it improved their mathematical skills, developed their confidence in their mathematical ability, their knowledge in analyzing and solving a problem, their communication skills, and their ability to ask inquiry questions. The positive effect of online collaboration is due to its appropriateness to the asynchronous learning implemented by CHED in schools and colleges and the flexibility of the learning modality (Purcell, Buchanan, and Friedrich, 2013; Condict, 2016; Dreamson, 2016; Reyes-Chua et al., 2020).

Online collaboration can improve learners' performance in Mathematics compared to the standard strategies implemented in the pandemic (Nguyen, 2015; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Lai, Wen, Gao, and Lin, 2020). Furthermore, even with the multitude of information available online, due to the cooperation among learners, it is easier for them to validate the data they gathered and ask for feedback from their peers and or instructor (Matranga and Koku, 2015; Kondakcui, 2020). The result goes against the claim that online learning and collaboration have no effects on the academic performance of the students (Demitriadou, Stavroulia, and Lanitis, 2020; Lee and Haggerty, 2020; Baticulon, 2021; Rowan and Murray, 2021).

Difference of the Motivation of Students' Exposed to OCL and Non-OCL

Intrinsic Goal Orientation

Table 21 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on motivation to learn online concerning intrinsic goal orientation.

Table 21. Comparison of students Motivation to Learn Online in relation to Intrinsic Goal Orientation (IGO)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.32	0.513		
non-OCL	51	3.77	0.622		
Total	98	4.03	0.633		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	7.257	1	7.257	22.023	0.000**
Pre-MLOQ (IGO)	0.139	1	0.139	0.422	0.518
Error	31.304				
TOTAL	1632.938				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 21, the pre-MLOQ in intrinsic goal orientation was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 22.023 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.32 has a higher intrinsic motivation than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.77, which would indicate a significant difference found in the students' intrinsic motivation based on the MLOQ result. As shown in Table 5, the students in the OCL group are intrinsically motivated than those in the non-OCL group who are only motivated intrinsically.

The study of Bonito (2013) and Malinauska and Pozeriene (2020) supports the result by stating that students who interact with other learners are more intrinsically motivated and even more so in an online setting where they can interact through social media. The OCL group has a higher mean due to the interactive nature of online collaboration and utilization of social media applications to supplement learning (Avila et al., 2020; Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020; Estira, 2020; Fernando, Thiry, Queiroz, and Fernandes, 2020; Sze, 2020;

Chua, 2021). Furthermore, online collaboration can contribute to the willingness of the students to learn and continue to learn due to the encouragement they receive from their peers (Aduayi-Akue et al., 2017; Fowler, 2017; Al-Nofaie, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021).

Extrinsic Goal Orientation

Table 22 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on motivation to learn online concerning extrinsic goal orientation.

Table 22. Comparison of students Motivation to Learn Online in relation to Extrinsic Goal Orientation (EGO)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.29	0.585		
non-OCL	51	3.84	0.626		
Total	98	4.05	0.644		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	4.889	1	4.889	13.138	0.000**
Pre-MLOQ (EGO)	5.44E-005	1	5.44E-005	0.000	0.990
Error	35.350				
TOTAL	1650.563				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 22, the pre-MLOQ in extrinsic goal orientation was used as a covariate to statistically equate different prognostic variables, which may affect the analysis. The f-value between groups is 13.138, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.29 has a higher extrinsic motivation than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.84, which would indicate a significant difference found in the students' extrinsic motivation based on the MLOQ result. As shown in Table 6, the students in the OCL group are highly motivated extrinsically than students in the non-OCL group who are only motivated extrinsically.

The study of Bonito (2013), Lee and Martin (2017) support the result by detailing that students who strive for good grades are more motivated to learn. The learners make this effort to attain good or excellent grades considered an

extrinsic factor of motivation (Fowler, 2017; Avila et al., 2020; Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021). Furthermore, with the collaboration system in place, learners are encouraged by their peers to do good and improve their academic performance, which contributes to their high extrinsic motivation (Elizabeth and John, 2012; Aduayu-Akue et al., 2017; Magen-Nagar and Shonfeld, 2018; Estira, 2020).

Control of Learning Beliefs

Table 23 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on motivation to learn online concerning the control of learning beliefs.

Table 23. Comparison of students Motivation to Learn Online in relation to Control of Learning Beliefs (CLB)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.30	0.587		
non-OCL	51	3.86	0.757		
Total	98	4.07	0.713		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	5.005	1	5.005	10.740	0.001**
Pre-MLOQ (CLB)	0.255	1	0.255	0.548	0.461
Error	44.269				
TOTAL	1673.875				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 23, the pre-MLOQ in control of learning beliefs was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 10.740 with a probability of 0.001 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.30 has a higher intrinsic motivation than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.86, which would indicate a significant difference found in the control of students' learning beliefs based on the MLOQ result. As shown in Table 7, the students in the OCL group are highly motivated to control their learning beliefs compared to the students in the non-OCL group, who are only motivated to control their learning beliefs.

The study of Bonito (2013) and Stockleben et al. (2017) supports the result by stating that collaboration in the online setting can help students regulate their learning beliefs. They can clarify their views with another student and even their instructor. The online classroom provides learners with opportunities to listen and engage with other students and help them control and promote their learning beliefs and even adjust them because of the interaction they have with other learners (Harandi, 2015; Fowler, 2017; Ahn and Edwin, 2018; Avila et al., 2020; Avila, Maria and Genio, 2020; Estira, 2020; Tammb, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021).

Self-Efficacy

Table 24 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on motivation to learn online concerning self-efficacy.

Table 24. Comparison of students Motivation to Learn Online in relation to Self-Efficacy (SE)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
OCL	47	4.03	0.607
non-OCL	51	3.69	0.494
Total	98	3.85	0.575

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	2.916	1	2.916	9.548	0.003**
Pre-MLOQ (SE)	0.148	1	0.148	0.483	0.489
Error	29.013				
TOTAL	1486.938				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 24, the pre-MLOQ in self-efficacy was used as a covariate to statistically equate different prognostic variables, which may affect the analysis. The f-value between groups is 9.548, with a probability of 0.003 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.03 has a higher self-efficacy than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.69, which would indicate that there is a difference found in the students' self-efficacy based on the MLOQ result.

This result supports the study of Bonito (2013) and Balser, Grabau, Knieess, and Page (2018), justifying that if learners cooperate, their efficacy to work in class would increase. Online learning can also increase the learners' self-efficacy in-class activities and tests because of the flexible nature of online learning (Kim and Frick, 2011; Fowler, 2017; Ucar and Goksel, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021). Furthermore, easy access to information can boost the students' efficiency and improve their belief in themselves (Harnadi, 2015; Condict, 2016; Avila et al., 2020; Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020; Estira, 2020).

Test Anxiety

Table 25 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on motivation to learn online concerning test anxiety.

Table 25. Comparison of students Motivation to Learn Online in relation to Test Anxiety (TA)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	2.22	1.005		
non-OCL	51	3.78	0.676		
Total	98	3.03	1.153		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	60.082	1	60.082	83.705	0.000**
Pre-MLOQ (TA)	1.097	1	1.097	1.529	0.219
Error	68.189				
TOTAL	1031.560				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 25, the pre-MLOQ in test anxiety was used as a covariate to statistically equate different prognostic variables, which may affect the analysis. The f-value between groups is 83.705, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 2.22 has lower test anxiety than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.78, which indicates a significant difference found in the students' test anxiety based on the MLOQ result. As shown in Table 9, the student in the

OCL group has low-test anxiety compared to the non-OCL group who has high-test anxiety.

Elizabeth and John (2012), Bonito (2013), and Mese and Sevilen (2021) support the result where learners are more confident in taking examinations if they have been reviewed or aided by a peer. Collaboration can foster students learning due to the social learning environment that promotes retention and learning for the student (Harasim, 2012; Fowler, 2017, Raymundo, 2020). The high-test anxiety of the students in the non-OCL group can be due to a lack of social interaction, and the social isolation that some students feel can increase the anxiety of a student, especially during exams (Aduayi-Akue et al., 2017; Tamma, 2020; Schaffhauser, 2020; Rowan and Murray, 2021).

Class Content

Table 26 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on motivation to learn online concerning class content.

Table 26. Comparison of students Motivation to Learn Online in relation to Class Content (CC)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
OCL	47	3.80	0.778
non-OCL	51	3.46	0.510
Total	98	3.62	0.670

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	2.083	1	2.083	4.914	0.029*
Pre-MLOQ (CC)	0.568	1	0.568	1.339	0.250
Error	40.280				
TOTAL	1329.487				

Note: * - Significant at 0.05 level

As observed in Table 26, the pre-MLOQ in class content was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 4.914, with a probability of 0.029 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 3.80 has a higher motivation to learn the class content

compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.46, which would indicate that there is a difference found in the motivation to learn the class content of the student based on the MLOQ result.

The study of Bonito (2013) and Makel et al. (2020) supports the result by stating that learners are more eager to learn the class contents if the students learn with their peers or in a group. The source of interest from one member of the group can also spark the interest of the rest (Chyung, Moll, and Berg, 2010; Fowler, 2017; Avila et al., 2020; Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020). Additionally, the students' access to many materials available on the internet can increase interest and motivation to learn on their own while referencing materials available in the class (Estira, 2020; Tammb, 2020; Ucak and Goksel, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021).

Social Engagement

Table 27 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on motivation to learn online concerning social engagement.

Table 27. Comparison of students Motivation to Learn Online in relation to Social Engagement (SE)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	3.66	0.630		
non-OCL	51	3.64	0.425		
Total	98	3.65	0.531		
Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	0.003	1	0.003	0.011	0.916
Pre-MLOQ (SE)	0.971	1	0.971	3.504	0.064
Error	26.319				
TOTAL	1333.640				

As observed in Table 27, the pre-MLOQ in social engagement was used as a covariate to statistically equate different prognostic variables, which may affect the analysis. The f-value between groups is 0.011 with a probability of 0.915 ($p > 0.05$), indicating no significant improvement. The result implies that

the OCL group with a mean of 3.66 has a similar motivation to engage socially, compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.64, which indicates no significant difference found in the social engagement of the students based on the MLOQ result. As shown in Table 11, the students in the OCL group and the non-OCL group are motivated to engage socially.

The study of Bonito (2013) and Pando (2018) supports the result by claiming that students are naturally interactive regardless of a structured organization in class and would find a method to interact with other students. The instructions given by the instructor guides students, and using their mobile devices and the internet, they tend to ask for help from their peers and friends (Avila et al., 2020; Avila, Maria, and Genio, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021). The strategy is a healthy way to learn in this time of pandemic because limiting their interaction may trigger the students' inhibition and cause social isolation (Huang, Kellert, and Manouchehri, 2015; Deniz and Simsek, 2015; Estira, 2020; Tammb, 2020; Mese and Sevilen, 2021).

Motivation to Learn Online

Table 28 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation and the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL rating on motivation to learn online.

Table 28. Comparison of students Motivation to Learn Online

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.07	0.367		
non-OCL	51	3.71	0.343		
Total	98	3.88	0.396		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	3.223	1	3.223	25.653	0.000**
Pre-MLOQ	0.134	1	0.134	1.068	0.304
Error	11.934				
TOTAL	1490.774				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 28, the pre-MLOQ was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-

value between groups is 25.625 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that the motivation of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning are the same, is rejected. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.07 has a higher motivation score than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.71, which would mean further that there is a significant difference found in their motivation to learn online based on the MLOQ result. Table 28 shows that both groups are motivated to learn online.

The study of Bonito (2013) and Hammond (2017) supports the claim that collaboration can help improve students' motivation to learn because of the structures and facilitated structure of OCL. Collaboration can improve students' motivation due to shared interests and similar goals that improve learning quality (Matranga and Koku, 2015; Fowler, 2017; Du et al., 2018; Raymundo, 2021). Elizabeth and John (2012) further support by claiming that increased sociability can increase the student's overall performance.

Furthermore, collaboration among members with the guidance of the instructor can help learners overcome the social isolation of the pandemic and help mitigate the loss of interest of learners in the online setting (Harasim, 2012; Tarum, 2019; Ucar and Goksel, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021). The result goes against the studies of Mese and Sevilen (2020) and Tamma (2020) that claimed that the negative impact on student motivation increases student anxiety. Moreover, the result contradicts the study of Cull (2010) and Demitriadou, Stavroulia, and Lanitis (2020), stating that online collaboration and learning do not affect the student's motivation.

Difference of the Effectiveness of Students' Exposed to OCL and Non-OCL

Purpose and Goals

Table 29 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL rating on effectiveness to learn online concerning purpose and goals.

Table 29. Comparison of students Effectiveness in relation to Purpose and Goal (PG)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.52	0.489		
non-OCL	51	3.59	1.054		
Total	98	4.04	0.950		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	21.464	1	21.464	31.641	0.000**
Pre-TEQ (PG)	2.069	1	2.069	3.050	0.084
Error	64.444				
TOTAL	1684.376				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 29, the pre-TEQ in purpose and goal was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 31.641 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.52 has higher effectiveness on their purpose and goals than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.59, which would indicate a significant difference found in the purpose and goals of the students based on the TEQ result. As shown in Table 12, the students in the OCL group have very high effectiveness in their purpose and goals compared to the students in the non-OCL group, who only have high motivation.

The study of Balsler, Grabau, Knieess, and Page (2018) supports the result that collaboration helps students form their purpose and goals in learning and attain them with their peers' support. Online classes establish the learning goal for students and support the learners to achieve their goals (Harasim, 2012; Nguyen, 2015; Dreamson, 2016, Dizon, 2020. This aspect of learning is due to the positive influence and flexible nature of online learning, making it easy for the students to set their purpose and accomplish their goal, with guidance provided by the instructor (Lee and Martin, 2017; Du et al., 2018; Shang and Chen, 2018; Maxwell, Smoker, and Stites-Doe, 2018; Sze, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021).

Role

Table 30 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on effectiveness to learn online concerning roles.

Table 30. Comparison of students Effectiveness in relation to Roles (Ro)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
OCL	47	4.50	0.508
non-OCL	51	3.68	1.047
Total	98	4.07	0.926

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	16.446	1	16.446	23.441	0.000**
Pre-TEQ (Ro)	0.034	1	0.034	0.049	0.825
Error	66.654				
TOTAL	1709.306				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 30, the pre-TEQ in roles was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 23.441 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.50 has a higher understanding of their roles than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.68, which would indicate a significant difference found in the effectiveness of understanding the students' role based on the TEQ result. As shown in Table 13, the students in the OCL group have very high effectiveness in understanding their roles than the non-OCL group, who only have high effectiveness in understanding their roles.

The study of Lam and Kapur (2018) and Andrade, Miller, Kunz, and Ratliff (2020) supports the result that it is easier for learners to establish and identify their roles since they are in a group and can assign the roles and functions to one another. Since online learning is self-paced, learners can easily associate and realize their roles in class (Harasim, 2012; Nguyen, 2015; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Dizon, 2020). Additionally, the effectiveness of understanding the learners' roles can be associated with the team dynamic

offered by collaborative learning (Dreamson, 2016; Kim and Park, 2018; Raymundo, 2020; Chua, 2021).

Process

Table 31 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL rating on effectiveness to learn online concerning the process.

Table 31. Comparison of students Effectiveness in relation to Process (P)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
OCL	47	4.40	0.523
non-OCL	51	3.72	0.804
Total	98	4.04	0.761

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	11.447	1	11.447	24.407	0.000**
Pre-TEQ (P)	0.334	1	0.334	0.712	0.401
Error	44.58				
TOTAL	1657.580				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 31, the pre-TEQ process was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 24.407 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.40 has higher effectiveness in the learning process than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.72, which would indicate a significant difference found in the process of the students based on the TEQ result. As shown in Table 14, the students in the OCL group have very high effectiveness in learning compared to the students in the non-OCL group, who only have high effectiveness.

The study of Makel et al. (2020) supports the result by stating that collaboration assists the learners to understand the process of learning due to the peer support offered and the feedback given by each member. The unrestricted availability of the information and the accessible communication with other learners creates an avenue to be engaged and facilitate their learning

(Gutierrez, 2013; Stephan, 2014; Nguyen, 2015; Hammond, 2017; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Dizon, 2020). Additionally, with the facilitation of learning, students can be more confident in the learning process and become more active in the decision-making process (Harasim, 2012; Matranga and Koku, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Magen-Nagar and Shonfeld, 2018; Gocotano et al., 2021).

Relationships

Table 32 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL rating on effectiveness to learn online concerning relationships.

Table 32. Comparison of students Effectiveness in relation to Relationship (Re)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.63	0.477		
non-OCL	51	3.82	0.940		
Total	98	4.21	0.855		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	16.364	1	16.364	28.472	0.000**
Pre-TEQ (Re)	0.037	1	0.037	0.064	0.801
Error	54.601				
TOTAL	1805.570				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 32, the pre-TEQ in the relationship was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 28.472, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.63 has higher effectiveness in establishing relationships than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.82, which indicates a significant difference found in the relationships of the students on the TEQ result. As shown in Table 15, the students in the OCL group have very high effectiveness in establishing relationships compared to the students in the non-OCL group who have high effectiveness.

The study of Stockleben et al. (2017) and Raymundo (2020) supports the result that the relationship between students in a group is more empowering in an online setting because a support system is offered when working collaboratively. The enhancement of the relationship is because of social media platforms that help facilitate communication between learners and instructors (Bates, 2014; Eric, 2015; Mantranga and Koku, 2015; Lee and Martin, 2017; Du et al., 2018; Gocotano et al., 2020). Furthermore, online learning can help facilitate learning by a healthy exchange of information and support to overcome challenges (Harasim, 2012; Condict, 2016; Makel et al., 2020).

Intergroup Relations

Table 33 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL rating on effectiveness to learn online concerning intergroup relations.

Table 33. Comparison of students Effectiveness in relation to Intergroup Relations (IR)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.23	0.539		
non-OCL	51	3.75	0.897		
Total	98	3.98	0.781		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	5.623	1	5.623	9.979	0.002**
Pre-TEQ (IR)	5.46E-006	1	5.46E-006	0.000	0.998
Error	53.531				
TOTAL	1608.185				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 33, the pre-TEQ in intergroup relations was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 9.979, with a probability of 0.002 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.23 has a more effective relationship with other groups or individuals compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.75, which would indicate that there is a significant difference found in the intergroup

relation of the student based on the TEQ result. As shown in Table 16, the students in the OCL group have very high effectiveness in establishing relationships with other groups or individuals compared to the students in the non-OCL group who have high effectiveness.

The study of Harasim (2012) and Stockleben et al. (2017) supports the result by establishing that students who work collectively are also concerned with helping other groups or individuals or are more concerned with benefiting the entire class. The success of online learning is the students' support for one another and implies that the success of one student is the success of the entire class (Deniz and Simsek, 2015; Mantranga and Koku, 2015; Hammond, 2017; Balser, Grabau, Knieess, and Page, 2018; Dizon, 2020). Additionally, the groups or learners have a common goal and interest to succeed in their learning; hence they assist one another that benefits both parties involve (Bates, 2014; Eric, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Raymundo 2020).

Problem Solving

Table 34 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL rating on effectiveness to learn online concerning problem-solving.

Table 34. Comparison of students Effectiveness in relation to Problem Solving (PS)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.40	0.533		
non-OCL	51	3.68	0.781		
Total	98	4.02	0.762		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	13.120	1	13.120	28.866	0.000**
Pre-TEQ (PS)	0.407	1	0.407	0.896	0.346
Error	43.179				
TOTAL	1641.523				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 34, the pre-TEQ in problem-solving was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 28.866, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.40 has higher effectiveness in solving problems than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.68, which would indicate a significant difference found in the problem solving of the students based on the TEQ result. As shown in Table 17, the student in the OCL group has higher effectiveness in solving a problem than the non-OCL group, who have high effectiveness.

The study of Harasim (2012) and Raymundo (2020) supports the result by asserting that students who work on a problem collaboratively are more likely to have a higher success rate than working alone. Online learning presents an overwhelming amount of information to students and challenges them (Nguyen, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Chua, 2021). Collaborative learning helps mitigate the burden on students, helps them adapt to the challenges, and encourages them to effectively solve the problems (Purcell, Buchanan, and Friedrich, 2013; Eric, 2015; Condict, 2016; Tucker et al., 2017; Gocotano et al., 2021).

Passion and Commitment

Table 35 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on effectiveness to learn online concerning passion and commitment.

Table 35. Comparison of students Effectiveness in relation to Passion and Commitment (PC)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.45	0.505		
non-OCL	51	3.81	0.755		
Total	98	4.12	0.719		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	9.953	1	9.953	23.530	0.000**
Pre-TEQ (PC)	0.040	1	0.040	0.093	0.761
Error	40.184				
TOTAL	1709.686				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As shown in Table 34, the pre-TEQ in passion and commitment was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 23.530 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.45 has higher effectiveness in identifying their passion and commitment to learning than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.81, which would indicate a significant difference found in the passion and commitment of the student to learn. As shown in Table 18, the student in the OCL group has very high effectiveness.

The study of Hammond (2017), Tarum (2019), and Raymundo (2020) supports the result by affirming that students cooperating can help cultivate the passion for learning and commitment to finish the task or activity. Collaborating can supplement the student's willingness to learn, and peers provide the needed encouragement to help learners persevere in online learning (Elizabeth and John, 2012; Nguyen, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Maxwell, Smoker, and Stites-Doe, 2018; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Bird, Castleman, and Ratliff, 2020; Dizon, 2020).

Skills and Learning

Table 36 shows the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL ratings on effectiveness to learn online concerning skills and learning.

Table 36. Comparison of students Effectiveness in relation to Skills and Learning (SL)

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	4.46	0.523		
non-OCL	51	3.86	0.765		
Total	98	4.15	0.724		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	9.341	1	9.341	22.254	0.000**
Pre-TEQ (SL)	2.003	1	2.003	4.772	0.031*
Error	39.876				
TOTAL	1738.640				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

* - Significant at 0.05 level

As observed in Table 36, the pre-TEQ in skills and learning was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 22.254 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), but the pre-TEQ in skills and learning has a probability of 0.031 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that there is no significant change. The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 4.46 has higher effectiveness in developing their skills and learning than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.86. However, the covariate would indicate that there is no significant improvement found in the skills and learning of the students based on the TEQ result. As shown in Table 19, the students in the OCL group have very high effectiveness in developing their skills and learning than the non-OCL group, who have high effectiveness.

The study of Hammond (2017) and Raymundo (2020) supports the result that establishes that learners in a collaborative group are more likely to develop their skills and improve their learning than those independently learning. Online learning can contribute to the development of the students, and learners are well-versed in information gathering when encountering a difficult task or topic (Purcell, Buchanan, and Friedrich, 2013; Nguyen, 2015; Dreamson, 2016; Tan and Vicente, 2019; Dizon, 2020). Furthermore, online learning can improve students' skills, especially in material validation; online platforms create an avenue for learners to explore and expand their understanding (Harasim, 2012; Shang and Chen, 2018; Abudmaid, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021).

Effectiveness

Table 37 shows the students' mean score with qualitative interpretation and the comparison between the OCL and Non-OCL rating on effectiveness to learn online.

Table 37. Comparison of students Effectiveness

GROUP	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION		
OCL	47	3.95	0.392		
non-OCL	51	3.32	0.713		
Total	98	3.62	0.660		

Source	SS	df	MS	f-value	p-value
Group	9.672	1	9.672	28.297	0.000**
Pre-TEQ	0.008	1	0.008	0.025	0.876
Error	32.470				
TOTAL	1329.735				

Note: ** - Significant at 0.01 level

As observed in Table 37, the pre-TEQ was used as a covariate to equate different prognostic variables, affecting the analysis statistically. The f-value between groups is 28.297 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant improvement. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that the team effectiveness of the students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning considering the dimensions are the same, is rejected.

The result implies that the OCL group with a mean of 3.95 has a higher rating than the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.32, which would further mean that there is a significant difference in the team effectiveness of the students based on the TEQ result. Also, the students in the OCL group have high effectiveness in learning online compared to the non-OCL group, who have displayed that there was no effect on their effectiveness to learn online.

The studies of Hammond (2017), Tarum (2019), and Makel et al. (2020) support the result by claiming that collaboration can improve student learning because of peer support and the feedback mechanism. Collaborating online can improve students' performance and overall learning experience (Harasim,

2012; Dreamson, 2016; Dizon, 2020; Raymundo, 2020; Gocotano et al., 2021). The result goes against the studies of Bird, Castleman, and Lohner (2020) and Baticulon et al. (2021), stating that online learning is ineffective in improving students learning, and online collaboration has the same effect as the standard instruction of online classes.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter summarizes the findings, conclusions, and recommendations on the students' academic achievement and motivation of virtual education via online collaborative learning.

Summary

The conduct of the study was to determine the level of academic achievement and degree of students' motivation in virtual education using online collaboration learning.

The OCL group had a mean percentage score of 46% in the pre-test, which shows that the student's scores are deficient, which indicates that they did not meet expectations. The non-OCL group has a mean percentage score of 48%, indicating that the student's scores are deficient, implying that they also did not meet the expectation. After implementing the intervention, the OCL group has a mean of 34.64 and a mean percentage score of 87% in the post-test, which shows that the student's score is above average, which indicates that they have a very satisfactory result. The non-OCL group has a mean of 30.10 and a mean percentage score of 75%, which specifies that the student's scores are below averages, indicating that they have a fair result. Notice that both groups have improved in their academic performance. The f-value between groups is 16.216, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant difference. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that the academic achievement of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning are the same, is rejected.

The comparison of motivation concerning intrinsic goal orientation shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.32 signifying that the students are highly motivated compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.77, pointing out

that the students are motivated. The f-value between groups is 22.023, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant difference in intrinsic goal orientation. The comparison of motivation concerning extrinsic goal orientation shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.29 implies that the students are highly motivated compared to the non-OCL with a mean of 3.84, signifying that the students are motivated. The f-value between groups is 13.138, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), showing a significant difference in extrinsic goal orientation. The comparison of motivation on the students' control of learning beliefs shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.30 points out that the students are highly motivated compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.86, implying that students are motivated. The f-value between groups is 10.740, with a probability of 0.001 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant difference in the extrinsic goal orientation.

The comparison of motivation concerning self-efficacy shows that OCL group with a mean of 4.03 and non-OCL group with a mean group of 3.69, stating that both groups were motivated. The f-value between groups is 9.548, with a probability of 0.003 ($p < 0.01$), implying a significant difference in self-efficacy. The comparison of motivation concerning testing anxiety shows that the OCL group with a mean of 2.22 shows that the students have low-test anxiety, contrary to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.78, indicating that the students have high-test anxiety. The f-value between groups is 83.705, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), showing a significant difference in test anxiety. The comparison of motivation concerning class content shows the OCL group with a mean of 3.80 and the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.46, stating the students are motivated. The f-value between groups is 4.914, with a probability of 0.029 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a significant difference in class content.

The comparison of motivation concerning social engagement shows the OCL group with a mean of 3.66 and the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.64, implying the students are motivated. The f-value between groups is 0.011 with a probability of 0.915 ($p > 0.05$), showing no significant difference in social engagement. The comparison of motivation to learn online shows the OCL group with a mean of 4.07 and the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.71 states

the students are motivated. The f-value between groups is 25.625, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant difference. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that the motivation of students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning are the same, is rejected.

The comparison of effectiveness concerning the purpose and goals shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.52 points out that the students have very high effectiveness compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.59, shows that the students have high effectiveness. The f-value between groups is 31.641, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant difference in purpose and goals. The comparison of effectiveness concerning roles shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.50, signifying that the students have very high effectiveness compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.68, states that the students have high effectiveness. The f-value between groups is 23.441, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), signifying a significant difference in roles. The comparison of effectiveness concerning the process shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.40 indicates that the students have very high effectiveness compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.72, which shows that the students have high effectiveness. The f-value between groups is 24.407 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), implying a significant difference in the process.

The comparison of effectiveness concerning relationships shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.63 shows that the student has very high effectiveness. The non-OCL with a mean of 3.82 implies that the students gave high effectiveness. The f-value between groups is 28.472, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), signifying a significant relationship difference. The comparison of effectiveness concerning intergroup relations shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.23 indicates that the student has very high effectiveness. The non-OCL group with a mean of 3.75 indicates that the students have high effectiveness. The f-value between groups is 9.979, with a probability of 0.002 ($p < 0.01$), which states a significant difference in the intergroup relations. The comparison of effectiveness concerning problem-solving shows that the OCL

group with a mean of 4.40 implies that the students have very high effectiveness compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.68, indicating that the student has high effectiveness. The f-value between groups is 28.866, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), showing a significant difference in problem-solving.

The comparison of effectiveness concerning passion and commitment shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.45 shows that the students have very high effectiveness compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.81, which implies that the student has high effectiveness. The f-value between groups is 23.530 with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant difference in passion and commitment. The comparison of effectiveness concerning skills and learning shows that the OCL group with a mean of 4.46, signifying that the students have very high effectiveness compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.86, points out that the student has high effectiveness. The f-value between groups is 22.254, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a significant difference in skills and learning.

The comparison of effectiveness shows that the OCL group with a mean of 3.95 indicates that the students have high effectiveness compared to the non-OCL group with a mean of 3.32, showing that the student is not affected by ineffectiveness. The f-value between groups is 28.297, with a probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), implying a significant difference. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that the team effectiveness of the students exposed to online collaborative learning and online non-collaborative learning considering the dimensions are the same, is rejected.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are extracted:

The OCL group has improved in performance and garnered a satisfactory result, while the non-OCL group has also improved but only earned a fair result based on the post-test scores. Both groups improved in their performance, but the OCL has obtained a higher level of improvement than the non-OCL group. The OCL group is highly motivated on intrinsic and extrinsic goal orientation and control of learning beliefs. It is motivated by self-efficacy, class content, and social engagement while having low test anxiety. The non-OCL group is motivated by six factors but has high test anxiety.

The OCL group has very high effectiveness in all the eight factors, while the non-OCL also has high effectiveness in all eight factors.

Students' performance in the OCL group has improved to an above-average level. In contrast, students' performance in the non-OCL group is reasonably satisfactory based on the post-test result. The mathematics performance of students exposed to OCL is significantly higher than those not exposed to OCL.

The motivation of students in the OCL group, considering the seven factors of motivation, is significantly higher than the students in the non-OCL group except for social engagement based on the MLOQ results. Thus, the OCL group has a higher motivation than the non-OCL group.

The effectiveness of students in the OCL group, considering the eight dimensions of effectiveness, is significantly higher than the students in the non-OCL based on the TEQ result. Thus, the OCL group has higher effectiveness than the non-OCL group.

Recommendation

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are listed:

Mathematics educators may consider using Online Collaborative Learning (OCL) as one strategy to improve the students' mathematical performance since it was found in the study that there is a significant difference in the mathematical performance in terms of their post-test.

Teachers and curriculum designers may find avenues to employ online collaborative learning since it enables students to interact online and become more interactive throughout the course, notably in this pandemic. Note that the OCL approach is preferable in strengthening students' Mathematics engagement and productivity for learning.

Educators and administrators may find ways to implement OCL to facilitate the students' learning to regulate their information through peer feedback and increase their learning effectiveness.

To keep the students highly productive and engaged in online learning, the curriculum makers may give particular attention to instances wherein online instruction enhances students' interactions within the class in crafting online curriculum-based instruction. Moreover, teachers and administrators may explore developing interventions which will support learners in establishing healthy relationships with their classmates, thus, empowering students to collaborate and value the impact of cooperation in their online learning process.

Teachers, administrators, and educational planners are encouraged to adopt the online collaborative learning approach to instruct students, define goals and objectives, and apply principles in the actual world.

Teachers, administrators, and curriculum developers may consider using online collaborative learning as a teaching method that is highly effective in immersing the learners in mathematical concepts, theories, and abstract notions. However, directing the learners to a healthy flow of information necessitates the teacher's ongoing facilitation and feedback.

Future researchers may conduct a similar study to improve students' motivation further and strengthen cognitive development using online collaborative learning. Furthermore, researchers may conduct a study to identify what made the difference. The implementation of this study method is highly encouraged.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A

Letter of Request to Conduct Study

Republic of the Philippines
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
Central Mindanao University
 University Town, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon

May 31, 2021

REV. FR. VIRGILIO H. DELFIN, CPA, DBM
 President
 San Isidro College

Fr. Virgilio H. Delfin:

Pax Christi!

The undersigned is a graduate student of Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon, taking up the degree Master of Science in Mathematics Education. Currently, I am working on my thesis entitled "STUDENT ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND MOTIVATION OF VIRTUAL MATHEMATICS VIA ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING" in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the said degree.

In this connection, I would like to humbly request permission that I may be allowed to administer the questionnaire to the Second- and Third-Year College students who are officially enrolled for the Academic Year 2020 – 2021 as the participants. Rest assured that all data gathered will be treated with utmost anonymity and confidentiality in adherence to existing research ethical standards.

I look forward to your most favorable consideration of this request.

Thank you very much and God Bless.

Respectfully yours,

EVAN P. TANA-ON
 Graduate Student

Noted:

RAUL C. ORONGAN, PhD
 Research Adviser

Recommending Approval:

EVANGELINE I. GARCIA, PhD
 Vice President for Academic Affairs

Approved:

FR. VIRGILIO H. DELFIN, CPA, DBM
 President

Appendix B

Letter of Request to Pilot Test Questionnaires

Republic of the Philippines
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
Central Mindanao University
 University Town, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon

May 27, 2021

REV. FR. VIRGILIO H. DELFIN, CPA, DBM
 President
 San Isidro College

THRU: EVANGELINE I. GARCIA, PhD
 Executive Vice President
 San Isidro College

Dr. Evangeline I. Garcia:

Pax Christil!

The undersigned is a graduate student of Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon, taking up the degree Master of Science in Mathematics Education. Currently, I am working on my thesis entitled "STUDENT ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND MOTIVATION OF VIRTUAL MATHEMATICS VIA ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING" in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the said degree.

In view hereof, may I humbly ask permission from your good office to conduct a pilot test of my questionnaire to the Fourth-Year College Students in your school who are officially enrolled for the Academic Year 2020 – 2021. Rest assured that all data gathered will be treated with utmost anonymity and confidentiality in adherence to existing research ethical standards.

I look forward to your most favorable consideration of this request.

Thank you very much and God Bless.

Respectfully yours,

[Redacted Signature]
EVANGELINE I. GARCIA
 Graduate Student

Noted:

[Redacted Signature]
RAUL C. ORONGAN, PhD
 Research Adviser

Approved:

[Redacted Signature]
EVANGELINE I. GARCIA, PhD
 Executive Vice President

Appendix C

Letter to Experts to Evaluate the Test-Items

Republic of the Philippines
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
Central Mindanao University
 University Town, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon

May 25, 2021

SOL G. SIMBULAN, PhD
 Dean, School of Education
 San Isidro College

Dr. Sol G. Simbulan:

Pax Christi!

I am currently enrolled at Central Mindanao University pursuing the degree of Master of Science in Mathematics Education, I am working on my research study entitled: "STUDENTS ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND MOTIVATION OF VIRTUAL MATHEMATICS VIA ONLINE COLLABORATION LEARNING."

In this connection, being one of the experts in the field of Mathematics Education and Research, may I humbly ask for your expertise to validate the content and structure of the instrument attached. Your input will be a big help in the instrument that will be used in my research prior to its field testing and gathering. I look forward to your most favorable consideration of this request.

Thank you for your assistance and God Bless.

Respectfully yours,

EVAN P. TANIA-ON
 Graduate Student

Noted:

RAUL C. ORONGAN, PhD
 Research Adviser

RECEIVED:

SOL G. SIMBULAN, PhD
 Dean, School of Education

Republic of the Philippines
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
Central Mindanao University
University Town, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon

May 25, 2021

EVANGELINE I. GARCIA, PhD
Vice President for Academic Affairs
San Isidro College

Dr. Evangeline I. Garcia:

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May 25, 2021

ANNA WILDA C. TADO, EdD
Vice President for Research and Extension
San Isidro College

Dr. Anna Wilda C. Tado

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Research Adviser

RECEIVED

ANNA WILDA C. TADO, EdD
Vice President for Research and Extension

Appendix D

Team Effectiveness Questionnaire

London Leadership Academy, National Health Service

Instruction: Read through the following statements carefully and check the circle on the column that most represents your perspective.

Legend: SA - Strongly Agree D - Disagree
 A - Agree SD - Strongly Disagree
 N - Neutral

PURPOSE AND GOALS	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. Our team has a meaningful, shared purpose.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. We are strongly committed to a shared mission.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. We focus on big-picture strategic issues as much as on day-to-day activities.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. We set and meet challenging goals.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. We consistently produce strong, measurable results.	<input type="radio"/>				
6. We make sure our work helps the organization achieve its goals.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. The mission and goals of my team are well aligned with the organization's mission and goals.	<input type="radio"/>				
ROLES	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. Team members clearly understand their roles.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. When an individual's role changes, an intentional effort is made to clarify it for everyone on the team.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. Team members understand one another's roles.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Everyone values what each member contributes to the team.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Team members avoid duplication of effort and make sure they are clear about who is doing what.	<input type="radio"/>				
6. When team members' roles change, specific plans are implemented to help them assume their new responsibilities.	<input type="radio"/>				

7. Overlapping or shared tasks and responsibilities do not create problems for team members.	<input type="radio"/>				
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PROCESS

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. Team problem solving results in effective solutions.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. We address and resolve issues quickly.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. People on my team are rewarded for being team players.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Group meetings are very productive.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Our team has mechanisms in place to monitor its results.	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Our team works with a great deal of flexibility so that we can adapt to changing needs.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. When we choose consensus decision-making, we do it effectively.	<input type="radio"/>				

RELATIONSHIPS

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. Team members appreciate one another's unique capabilities.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. Team members are effective listeners.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. Communication in our group is open and honest.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Members of our team trust each other.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Team members help one another deal with problems or resolve issues	<input type="radio"/>				
6. We are able to work through differences of opinion without damaging relationships.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Team members display high levels of cooperation and mutual support.	<input type="radio"/>				

INTERGROUP RELATIONS

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. We are able to resolve conflicts with other teams collaboratively.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. We seek to arrange our priorities to meet the needs of other work groups.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. We communicate effectively with other groups.	<input type="radio"/>				

4. Our team has established trusting and supportive relationships with other teams.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. We work toward integrating our plans with those of other work groups.	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Our collaborations with other teams are productive, worthwhile, and yield good results.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. The goals of our group support those of other groups.	<input type="radio"/>				

PROBLEM SOLVING

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. Team members take personal responsibility for the effectiveness of our team.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. Team members maintain a can-do approach when they encounter frustrating situations.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. Team members take initiative to resolve issues between themselves without involving the team leader.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. We spend very little time complaining about things we cannot control.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Team members seek and give each other constructive feedback.	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Team members are sure about what is expected of them and take pride in a job well done.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Team members consider how their actions will impact others when deciding what to do.	<input type="radio"/>				

PASSION AND COMMITMENT

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. Working on our team inspires people to do their best.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. My team has a strong sense of accomplishment relative to our work.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. People are proud to be part of our team.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Team members frequently go beyond what is required and do not hesitate to take initiative.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. As a team, we work to attract and retain top performers.	<input type="radio"/>				

6. Our team is excited about the contribution it is making to the organization's competitive viability.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. My team is proud of its accomplishments and optimistic about the future.	<input type="radio"/>				

SKILLS AND LEARNING

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. We have the skills we need to do our jobs effectively.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. We always ask ourselves, "How can we do better tomorrow what we did today?"	<input type="radio"/>				
3. As a team, we are continually working to improve cycle time, speed to market, customer responsiveness, or other key performance indicators.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. We view everything, even mistakes, as opportunities for learning and growth.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. We use various forms of training to keep our skills up-to-date.	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Team members embrace continuous improvement as a way of life.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Team members work to ensure we are using best practice methods.	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix E

Motivation to Learn Online Questionnaire

Shawn Fowler (2017)

Instruction: Read through the following statements and assess yourself, then check the circle that most represents your answer.

Legend: SA - Strongly Agree D - Disagree
 A - Agree SD - Strongly Disagree
 N - Neutral

INTRINSIC GOAL ORIENTATION					
	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. I prefer material that really challenges me, so I can learn new things.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. I prefer material that arouses my curiosity, even if it's difficult to learn.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. The most satisfying thing for me is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. I choose assignments that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade.	<input type="radio"/>				
EXTERNAL GOAL ORIENTATION					
	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. Getting a good grade is the most satisfying thing for me.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. The most important thing for me is to improve my overall grade point average, so my concern is getting a good grade.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. I want to get better grades than most of the other students in my classes.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. I want to do well in my classes because it's important to show my ability to my family, friends, employer, or others.	<input type="radio"/>				
CONTROL OF LEARNING BELIEFS					
	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. If I study in appropriate ways, then I'll be able to learn the material.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. It's my own fault if I don't learn the material taught.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. If I try hard enough, then I'll understand the material presented.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. If I don't understand the material presented, it's because I didn't try hard enough.	<input type="radio"/>				

SELF-EFFICACY

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. I believe I'll receive excellent grades in my classes.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. I'm certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the readings.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. I'm confident I can learn the basic concepts that are being taught.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. I'm confident I can understand the most complex material presented by the instructor.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. I'm confident I can do an excellent job on assignments and tests.	<input type="radio"/>				
6. I expect to do well.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. I'm certain I can master the skills being taught.	<input type="radio"/>				
8. Considering the difficulty of the classes, the teachers, and my skills, I think I can do well.	<input type="radio"/>				

TEST ANXIETY

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. When I take tests, I think about how poorly I'm doing compared with other students.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. When I take tests, I think about items on other parts of the tests I can't answer.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. When I take tests, I think of the consequences of failing.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. I have an uneasy, upset feeling when I take exams.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. When taking exams, I feel my heart beating fast.	<input type="radio"/>				

CLASS CONTENT

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. I enjoy online classes.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. I learn the content well in online classes.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. I have control over my learning process.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Classes are easy for me.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. I choose online classes because they fit my personal schedule.	<input type="radio"/>				
6. I think my online classes are challenging.	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Cheating on online tests is easy.	<input type="radio"/>				

SOCIAL ENGAGEMENT

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. I feel "disconnected" from my teacher and fellow students in classes.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. I pay attention in online classes.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. I enjoy online class discussions.	<input type="radio"/>				
4. I feel like I can freely communicate with other students in online classes.	<input type="radio"/>				
5. I feel like I can freely communicate with the instructor in online classes.	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix F

Test Items and TOS

TABLE OF SPECIFICATION (TOS)
STATISTICS

TOPIC	No. of Meetings	No. of Items	%	Remembering	Understanding	Application	Analysis	Evaluating	Creating	Item Placement
Measures of Central Tendency	2	10	25	2	3	1	2	2		1 – 10
Measures of Dispersion	2	10	25		2	6	2			11 – 20
Sampling Techniques	2	10	25		2	2	4	2		21 – 30
Hypothesis Testing	2	10	25	1	3	1	2	3		31 – 40
TOTAL	8	40	100%	3	10	10	10	7		

SAN ISIDRO COLLEGE

City of Malaybalay, Bukidnon

PRE-TEST/POST TEST

STATISTICS

Name [Family Name, Given Name. Middle Initial]:

Student Number:

Course and Year:

Instruction: Read each item carefully and answer by blackening the circle of the option that corresponds to your answer.

1. The median of an ordered set of data is the value that represents _____?
 the mean of the squared deviation of the values from the mean
 the most frequently observed value
 the arithmetic average of the data values
 the middle or approximate middle of the data set
2. On your first 5 statistics tests, you received the following scores: 72, 86, 92, 63, and 77. What test score must you earn on your sixth test so that your average (mean score) for all six tests will be 80?
 90
 86
 95
 80
3. Following are the disadvantages of the Mean EXCEPT?
 Does not possess the desired algebraic property
 Cannot be computed if there are missing values due to omission or non-response.
 Easily affected by extreme values
 The mean cannot be computed in grouped data with open-ended class intervals
4. If the distribution is asymmetric, which measure of location is most appropriate a if the data is in a nominal scale? b If it is in an ordinal scale? (c) If it is in an interval or ratio scale?
 a Median, b mean, (c) mode
 a Mode, b median, (c) mean
 a Mode, b mode, (c) median
 a Median, b median, (c) median

5. Which of the following is **NOT** a characteristic of the mean?
- It minimizes the sum of squared deviations.
 - It is affected by extreme scores.
 - It is best used with ordinal data.
 - The sum of the deviations about the mean is 0.
6. If the distribution is asymmetric and the variable is measured on a nominal scale, the _____ should be used as a measure of location.
- Mean
 - Maxima
 - Median
 - Mode
7. Suppose a researcher is concerned with a nominal scale that identifies users versus non-users of bank credit cards, the measure of central tendency appropriate to this scale is the _____?
- Average
 - Median
 - Mode
 - Mean
8. The mean of 40 observations was 160. It was detected on re-checking that the value 165 was wrongly copied as 125 for computation of mean. Find the correct mean.
- 4
 - 151
 - 161
 - 650
9. Percentiles divide the series into?
- Two equal parts
 - Hundred equal parts
 - Four equal parts
 - None of the mentioned
10. A combined mean is _____?
- when mean of two or more than two series is computed collectively.
 - when mean of one or more than two series is computed collectively.
 - when mean of three or more than two series is computed collectively.
 - when mean of only two series is computed collectively.
11. When should measures of location and dispersion be computed from grouped data rather than from individual data values?
- Only when the data are from a population.
 - Whenever the computation is easier.
 - Only when individual data values are unavailable.
 - Whenever computer packages for descriptive statistics are unavailable.

12. Calculate mean deviation from mean for the following data: 100, 150, 200, 250, 360, 490, 500, 600, 671
- 174.44
- 178.23
- 173.45
- 172.56
13. A good dispersion should have the following characteristics EXCEPT?
- It should be rigidly defined
- It should be simple to understand
- It should lend itself for algebraic manipulation
- It should be based on extreme values
14. Calculate the standard deviation from the following data. 14, 22, 9, 15, 20, 17, 12, 11
- 2.15
- 4.15
- 3.18
- 4.18
15. Compute Mean deviation from mean and median from the following data:
- | Height (cm) | 158 | 159 | 160 | 161 | 162 | 163 | 164 | 165 | 166 |
|----------------|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|
| No. of Persons | 15 | 20 | 32 | 35 | 33 | 22 | 30 | 10 | 8 |
- 1.68
- 1.25
- 1.23
- 1.74
16. The table below gives the marks obtained by 10 students in statistics. Calculate standard deviation
- | Student | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 | 8 | 9 | 10 |
|---------|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|
| Marks | 43 | 48 | 65 | 57 | 31 | 60 | 37 | 48 | 78 | 59 |
- 13.42
- 12.23
- 13.26
- 14.41
17. Which of the following is TRUE about the variance?
- Involves squaring deviation scores and then dividing them together.
- Adjusted when to generalizing from a sample to a population.
- Cannot be calculated on continuous data.
- Produces small values in square units due to taking the square root of deviations.
18. What would happen to the variance of a data set if we added 5 to every observation?
- Variance increase by 5
- Variance decrease by 10
- Variance decrease by 5
- No Change

19. Find the mean deviation from the following series:

Age in Years	0-10	10-20	20-30	30-40	40-50	50-60	60-70	70-80
No. of Person	20	25	32	40	42	35	10	8

- 13.24
 15.14
 21.14
 12.16
20. Which of the following is false regarding dispersion?
- Reveals how items are spread out on either side of the center
 Indicates high or low uniformity of the items
 Serves to locate the distribution
 Difference or variation among the values
21. Which is the best format to use if content and material gathered for certain number of students by different interviews have to be compared in a piece of research?
- Projective
 Structured
 Unstructured
 Analytical
22. What best describes the Likert technique of attitude measurement?
- Subjects indicate whether they agree with each of a series of attitude statements which are equally spaced along an attitude continuum.
 Subjects indicate on five point scales the extent of their agreement with a set of attitude statements.
 Subjects judge a particular concept on a series of bipolar semantic scale.
 Subjects response to an open-ended interview are coded by content analyst.
23. A researcher wants to investigate the relationships between the use of drugs and study results of university students. The researcher would like to generalize the results to the population. Which kind of sample should the researcher use?
- Stratified Sampling
 Judgment Sampling
 Simple Random Sampling
 Quota Sampling
24. A large corporation wants to find out which benefit plans its employees would prefer. Which procedure would be most likely to obtain a statistically unbiased sample?
- Surveying a random sample of employees from a list of all employees.
 Inviting all employees to indicate their choices by e-mail.
 Placing suggestion boxes at random locations in the company's plant and offices.
 Assembling a group with one member from each department and recording the preferences of these employees.

25. A College President wants to find out which courses students consider to be of the most benefit to them. Which procedure would be most likely to produce a statistically unbiased sample?
- Asking students to mail in a questionnaire
 - Surveying a random sample of students taken from the list of all students
 - Surveying the first hundred students on an alphabetical list
 - Having students complete a questionnaire on the college web site
26. The discrepancies between the estimate and the population parameter is known as?
- Sampling error
 - Non-sampling error
 - Formula error
 - None of the options
27. Which of the following is not a characteristic of quota sampling?
- The researcher chooses who to approach and this might bias the sample.
 - Those who are available to be surveyed in public places are unlikely to constitute a representative sample.
 - The random selection of units makes it possible to calculate the standard error.
 - It is a relatively fast and cheap way of finding out about public opinions.
28. When a research company polls residents about their voting intentions, lumads are under-represented. This is an example of?
- Sampling bias
 - Response bias
 - Non-response bias
 - Measurement bias
29. What effect does increasing the sample size have upon the sampling error?
- It reduces the sampling error
 - It increases the sampling error
 - It has no effect on the sampling error
 - None of the options
30. Snowball sampling can help the researcher to _____?
- Access deviant or hidden populations
 - Theorize inductively in a qualitative study
 - Overcome the problem of not having an accessible sampling frame
 - All of the options

31. Generalized conclusion on the basis of a sample is technically known as _____?
- Data analysis and interpretation
 - Parameter inference
 - Statistical inference
 - All of the options
32. What can increase the power of a statistical test?
- Decreasing the size of the sample
 - Avoiding the use of the null hypothesis
 - Designing for small error effects
 - Avoiding random sampling.
33. Which is not the effective way of controlling a nuisance variable in an experimental design?
- Excluding the variable as one of the factors in the experiment
 - Exercising statistical control
 - Random assignment of subjects
 - Holding the nuisance variable constant for all subjects.
34. The p-value in hypothesis testing represents which of the following?
- The probability of failing to reject the null hypothesis, given the observed results
 - The probability that the null hypothesis is true, given the observed results
 - The probability that the observed results are statistically significant, given that the null hypothesis is true
 - The probability of observing results as extreme or more extreme than currently observed, given that the null hypothesis is true
35. Assume that the difference between the observed, paired sample values is defined in the same manner and that the specified significance level is the same for both hypothesis tests. Using the same data, the statement that "a paired/dependent two sample t-test is equivalent to a one sample t-test on the paired differences, resulting in the same test statistic, same p-value, and same conclusion" is:
- Always True
 - Never True
 - Sometimes True
 - Not Enough Information

36. A researcher believes that the proportion of individuals with diagnosed epilepsy that present with a depressive disorder, p_E , is higher than the proportion of individuals without diagnosed epilepsy that present with a depressive disorder, p_{NE} . Testing this claim, the researcher computed for the p-value which resulted in 0.003. Using a 0.10 significance level, which of the following is the most appropriate conclusion given the results?
- Reject the null hypothesis; there is sufficient evidence to support the researcher's claim.
- Fail to reject the null hypothesis; there is sufficient evidence to support the researcher's claim.
- Accept the null hypothesis; there is not sufficient evidence to support the researcher's claim.
- Accept the null hypothesis; there is sufficient evidence to support the researcher's claim.
37. The point where the Null Hypothesis gets rejected is called as _____?
- Significant Value
- Rejection Value
- Acceptance Value
- Critical Value
38. Type 1 error occurs when _____?
- we reject the null hypothesis if it is True.
- we reject the null hypothesis if it is False.
- we accept the null hypothesis if it is True.
- we accept the null hypothesis if it is False.
39. Which of the following is defined as the rule or formula to test a Null Hypothesis?
- Test statistic
- Population statistic
- Variance statistic
- Null statistic
40. A sociologist focusing on popular culture and media believes that the average number of hours per week (hours/week) spent using social media is greater for women than for men. Examining two independent simple random samples of 100 individuals each, the researcher calculates sample standard deviations of 2.3 hours/week and 2.5 hours/week for women and men respectively. If the average number of hours/week spent using social media for the sample of women is 1 hour greater than that for the sample of men, what conclusion can be made from a hypothesis test where:
- $$\begin{cases} H_0: \mu_W - \mu_M = 0 \\ H_A: \mu_W - \mu_M > 0 \end{cases}$$
- The observed difference in average number of hours/week spent using social media is not significant.
- The observed difference in average number of hours/week spent using social media is significant.
- A conclusion is not possible without knowing the average number of hours/week spent using social media in each sample
- A conclusion is not possible without knowing the population sizes.

Appendix G

Sample Lesson Plan

A. Lesson plan for the Online Collaborative Learning Group

LESSON PLAN FOR STATISTICS

INSTRUCTOR:	Evan P. Taja-on
LEVEL:	Second Year College
TIME:	43 minutes
TOPIC:	Measures of Central Tendency
SUBTOPIC:	Measures of Central Tendency: Ungrouped Data
SKILL(S) IN FOCUS:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team-Work - Mathematical Analysis - Critical Thinking - Authentic Application of Concepts
OBJECTIVES:	<p>at the end of the lesson, the learners must have;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. explain the importance of measures of central tendency; 2. calculate and interpret the mode, the median, and the mean; 3. identify the relative strengths and weaknesses of the three measures; and 4. determine and explain the shape of the distribution.
REFERENCES:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Module 5 – Measures of Central Tendency: Ungrouped Data - Black, K. <i>Business Statistics for Contemporary Decision Making</i>. Unit I: Descriptive Statistics – Measures of Central Tendency: Ungrouped Data, pp. 47 – 54 - Heumann C. and Shalabh, M.S. <i>Introduction to Statistics and Data Analysis with Exercises, Solution and Application</i>. Part 1: Descriptive Statistics – Measures of Central Tendency, pp. 37 - 45
PROCEDURE:	<p>A. Before the Lesson</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare the classroom by informing and admitting the learners into the online class. - Prayer <p style="margin-left: 40px;"><u>Review:</u> Ask the following question/s:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “What are your ideas/ experiences about measures of central tendency?” - “What do you remember about computing the mean?” - “What are your ideas about ungrouped data?” <p style="margin-left: 40px;">Ask around 2 to 4 students to answer the question</p> <p>B. During the Lesson</p> <p style="margin-left: 40px;">Working Definition:</p>

- Yield information about the center, or middle part, of a group of numbers.
- Do not focus on the span of the data set or how far values are from the middle numbers.

Mode:

- The most frequently occurring value in a set of data.

- Example:

7.00	11.00	14.25	15.00	15.00
15.50	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00
21.00	22.00	23.00	24.00	25.00
27.00	27.00	28.00	34.22	43.25

- The mode of this data set is 19.00

Median:

- The middle value in an ordered array of numbers.
- For an array with an even number of terms, the median is the average of the two middle numbers.
- Steps in getting the median of the data set;

STEP 1: Arrange the observations in an ordered data array.

STEP 2: For an odd number of terms, find the middle term of the ordered array. It is the median.

STEP 3: For an even number of terms, find the average of the middle two terms. This average is the median.

- Example:

Suppose a business researcher wants to determine the median for the following numbers.

15	11	14	3	21	17	22	16	19	16
5	7	19	8	9	20	4			

The researcher arranges the numbers in an ordered array.

3	4	5	7	8	9	11	14	
15	16	16	17	19	19	20	21	22

Because the array contains 17 terms (an odd number of terms), the median is the middle number, or 15.

Mean:

- Also known as the Arithmetic Mean.
- The average of a group of numbers and is computed by summing all numbers and dividing by the number of numbers.
- Equations for the mean:

- Population Mean

	$\mu = \frac{\sum x}{N} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_N}{N}$ <p>- Sample Mean</p> $\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_n}{n}$ <p>- Example:</p> $\begin{array}{r} 24 \\ 13 \\ 19 \\ 26 \\ \hline \Sigma x = 93 \end{array} \quad \mu = \frac{\sum x}{N} = \frac{93}{5} = 18.6$ <p>C. After the Lesson (Online class would end and the learners would proceed to their seatwork)</p> <p>- Instruction: Communicate with your groupmates and discuss amongst yourself on the given problem. You can ask questions and clarification in our group chat.</p> <p>1. The 2000 Philippine Census asked every household to report information on each person living there. Suppose for a sample of 30 households selected, the number of persons living in each was reported as follows.</p> $\begin{array}{cccccccccccccccc} 2 & 3 & 1 & 2 & 6 & 4 & 2 & 1 & 5 & 3 & 2 & 3 & 1 & 2 & 2 \\ 1 & 3 & 1 & 2 & 2 & 4 & 2 & 1 & 2 & 8 & 3 & 2 & 1 & 1 & 3 \end{array}$ <p>Compute the mean, median, and mode for these data.</p> <p>2. The 2000 Philippine Census also asked for each person's age. Suppose that a sample of 40 households taken from the census data showed the age of the first person recorded on the census form to be as follows.</p> $\begin{array}{cccccccccccccccc} 42 & 29 & 31 & 38 & 55 & 27 & 28 & 33 & 49 & 70 & 25 & 21 & 38 & 47 \\ 63 & 22 & 38 & 52 & 50 & 41 & 19 & 22 & 29 & 81 & 52 & 26 & 35 & 38 \\ 29 & 31 & 48 & 26 & 33 & 42 & 58 & 40 & 32 & 24 & 34 & 25 \end{array}$ <p>Compute mean, median, and mode for these data.</p>
ASSESSMENT:	Answer your quiz for the topic using the link: https://forms.gle/mbHZrj5CNmVWHAvn9

B. Lesson plan for the Online Non-Collaborative Learning Group

LESSON PLAN FOR STATISTICS

INSTRUCTOR:	Evan P. Taja-on
LEVEL:	Second Year College
TIME:	80 minutes
TOPIC:	Measures of Central Tendency
SUBTOPIC:	Measures of Central Tendency: Ungrouped Data
SKILL(S) IN FOCUS:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mathematical Analysis - Critical Thinking - Authentic Application of Concepts
OBJECTIVES:	<p>at the end of the lesson, the learners must have;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. explain the importance of measures of central tendency; 2. calculate and interpret the mode, the median, and the mean; 3. identify the relative strengths and weaknesses of the three measures; and 4. determine and explain the shape of the distribution.
REFERENCES:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Module 5 – Measures of Central Tendency: Ungrouped Data - Black, K. <i>Business Statistics for Contemporary Decision Making</i>. Unit I: Descriptive Statistics – Measures of Central Tendency: Ungrouped Data, pp. 47 – 54 - Heumann C. and Shalabh, M.S. <i>Introduction to Statistics and Data Analysis with Exercises, Solution and Application</i>. Part 1: Descriptive Statistics – Measures of Central Tendency, pp. 37 - 45
PROCEDURE:	<p>A. Before the Lesson</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare the classroom by informing and admitting the learners into the online class. - Prayer <p style="padding-left: 40px;"><u>Review:</u> Ask the following question/s:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “What are your ideas/ experiences about measures of central tendency?” - “What do you remember about computing the mean?” - “What are your ideas about ungrouped data?” <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Ask around 2 to 4 students to answer the question</p> <p>B. During the Lesson</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Working Definition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yield information about the center, or middle part, of a group of numbers.

- Do not focus on the span of the data set or how far values are from the middle numbers.

Mode:

- The most frequently occurring value in a set of data.

- Example:

7.00	11.00	14.25	15.00	15.00
15.50	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00
21.00	22.00	23.00	24.00	25.00
27.00	27.00	28.00	34.22	43.25

- The mode of this data set is 19.00

Median:

- The middle value in an ordered array of numbers.
- For an array with an even number of terms, the median is the average of the two middle numbers.
- Steps in getting the median of the data set;

STEP 1: Arrange the observations in an ordered data array.

STEP 2: For an odd number of terms, find the middle term of the ordered array. It is the median.

STEP 3: For an even number of terms, find the average of the middle two terms. This average is the median.

- Example:

Suppose a business researcher wants to determine the median for the following numbers.

15 11 14 3 21 17 22 16 19 16
5 7 19 8 9 20 4

The researcher arranges the numbers in an ordered array.

3 4 5 7 8 9 11 14
15 16 16 17 19 19 20 21 22

Because the array contains 17 terms (an odd number of terms), the median is the middle number, or 15.

Mean:

- Also known as the Arithmetic Mean.
- The average of a group of numbers and is computed by summing all numbers and dividing by the number of numbers.
- Equations for the mean:
- Population Mean

$$\mu = \frac{\sum x}{N} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_N}{N}$$

	<p>- Sample Mean</p> $\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_n}{n}$ <p>- Example:</p> <table style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">24</td> <td rowspan="5" style="padding: 0 10px;">$\mu = \frac{\sum x}{N} = \frac{93}{5} = 18.6$</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">13</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">19</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">26</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;"><u>11</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">$\sum x = 93$</td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <p>C. After the Lesson</p> <p>- Instruction: Answer the following problems by yourself. You are free to ask question.</p> <p>1. The 2000 Philippine Census asked every household to report information on each person living there. Suppose for a sample of 30 households selected, the number of persons living in each was reported as follows.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">2 3 1 2 6 4 2 1 5 3 2 3 1 2 2 1 3 1 2 2 4 2 1 2 8 3 2 1 1 3</p> <p>Compute the mean, median, and mode for these data.</p> <p>2. The 2000 Philippine Census also asked for each person's age. Suppose that a sample of 40 households taken from the census data showed the age of the first person recorded on the census form to be as follows.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">42 29 31 38 55 27 28 33 49 70 25 21 38 47 63 22 38 52 50 41 19 22 29 81 52 26 35 38 29 31 48 26 33 42 58 40 32 24 34 25</p> <p>Compute mean, median, and mode for these data.</p>	24	$\mu = \frac{\sum x}{N} = \frac{93}{5} = 18.6$	13	19	26	<u>11</u>	$\sum x = 93$	
24	$\mu = \frac{\sum x}{N} = \frac{93}{5} = 18.6$								
13									
19									
26									
<u>11</u>									
$\sum x = 93$									
ASSESSMENT:	<p>Answer your quiz for the topic using the link: https://forms.gle/mbHZrj5CNmVWHAvn9</p>								

Appendix H

DOCUMENTATION OF CONDUCT

A. Online Collaborative Group

Statistics Group 1

- Customize Chat
- Group Options
- Chat members
 - Julian Cristian Rodriguez**
Group creator
 - Isabelle Rodriguez**
Added by
 - Alexis Victoria Gonzalez**
Added by
 - Blanca Maria Dalia Torres**
Added by
 - Montague Maria Wilson**
Added by
 - Jazlin Michelle Gonzalez Rodriguez**
Added by

Statistics Group 5
Active Now

- Customize Chat
- Chat members
 - Wagner Christian Gonzalez Rodriguez**
Group creator
 - Jennifer de la Cruz de Santa**
Added by
 - Bryan Pacifico Carrero**
Added by
 - Honey Jay Rodriguez**
Added by
 - Ryan Taji**
Added by

Statistics Group 9

Customize Chat

Chat members

-

Richard Lumbana Balde
Group creator

⋮
-

Jay R
Added by I

⋮
-

Evan Taja-on
Added by I

⋮
-

Hamilton Willy Galan Wilson
Added by I

⋮
-

Joseph Theo Moral Lancia
Added by I

⋮
-

Rorie Way Casperino Serrano
Added by I

⋮
-

Kim Lina
Added by I

⋮

A.1. Sample Conversation

Statistics Group 9
Active now

Annie Grace unsent a message

←

replied to

Nag end na ang orientation?

yes, miss. taod taod na pod nahuman si sir.

I can send you screenshots of what has been discussed, If you want.

Okay thank you

Sige diri nalang pa send thank you maam

B. Online Non-Collaborative Group

Appendix I

GRAMMAR AND PLAGIARISM RESULT

SAN ISIDRO COLLEGE

Office of the Vice President for Research
Extension & Development

Implamabong, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon
Tel (088) 813-5541; Website: sic.edu.ph; Webmail: info@sic.edu.ph

GRAMMARLY TEST AND PLAGIARISM TEST REPORT

Name : EVAN P. TAJA-ON
Course : MASTERS OF SCIENCE IN MATHEMATICS
EDUCATION
Title of Study : STUDENT ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND
MOTIVATION OF VIRTUAL MATHEMATICS VIA
ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING
Adviser : DR. RAUL C. ORONGAN
Date Submitted : 12.06.2021
Date Released : 12.06.2021
Pass No. : ___ First Second

	<i>Grammarly Score</i>	<i>Remark</i>	<i>Plagiarized</i>	<i>Remark</i>
Chapter 1	97	PASSED	2	PASSED
Chapter 2				
Chapter 3				
Chapter 4				
Chapter 5				

Prepared by:

ANNA WILDA C. TADO, Ed.D.
Vice President for Research, Extension and Development